

Report on Research Line 7

Cycling Initiatives for an Inclusive Mobility Transition

Insights from ACCTING's Experimental Research

Research Cycle 2

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The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

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Introduction and methodology

1. Introduction

This report presents a summary of findings from Research Line 7 of ACCTING's second cycle of experimental studies, which draws on data gathered from 87 quasi-experimental case studies conducted across thirteen countries between December 2023 and August 2024. Each research line explores sustainability and behavioural change within the framework of a specific European Green Deal policy area—including climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. This report focuses on *transport poverty and sustainable travel, and more specifically on cycling initiatives*, examining how policies can support more inclusive and environmentally responsible mobility.

All reports are available at <https://accting.eu/project-deliverables/>

1.1 Cycling initiatives for an inclusive mobility transition in the EU

This report focuses on how cycling initiatives and programmes *can contribute to an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal*. In particular, RL7 focuses on the impact such initiatives or programmes can have on behavioural change among vulnerable groups of people and/or people living in vulnerable areas; and how and what they can contribute to cycling inclusion. The research questions guiding the second research cycle of RL7 were:

- To what extent and how do cycling initiatives reduce barriers for marginalised groups/individuals to take up cycling?
- How do different interventions for cycling inclusion unfold on which groups, and with what gender+ intersectional effects?
- How can cycling initiatives contribute to an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal?

In short, the research *focuses on how cycling initiatives can help their participants to overcome barriers to cycling (or not), and what factors are important to make this happen*. These insights, in turn, help to shed light on whether and how Green Deal measures can contribute to achieving an inclusive and socially just transition.

The EU 2030 Climate target plan sets out to lower congestion and pollution from transport. To succeed, there is a need for increased modal shares of collective transport, walking and cycling. Cycling specifically “contributes to the EU’s green transition by reducing road congestion and noise pollution, and by improving air quality.”¹²

¹<https://epthinktank.eu/2023/02/16/towards-a-european-cycling-strategy/#:~:text=Cycling%20was%20also%20mentioned%20in,and%20cycling%20and%20walking%20infrastucture.>

² [2021-mobility-strategy-and-action-plan.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

Research on sustainable transport has focused on how to best plan for and reduce the use of cars while promoting more energy-efficient modes of transport such as cycling. It has also focused on making cycling safer, more attractive, and more accessible (Parkin 2012). For example, research on cycling and sustainability reveals the advantages of cycling compared to motor traffic as it produces less greenhouse gases, noise or emissions; it causes few accidents, and bicycles take up little space when parked or in use (Börjesson & Eliasson 2012, 248).

Cycling however presents a paradox (van der Kloof 2022): At first glance, cycling seems to be “for everyone”, and in theory, cycling is a comparably cheap and easily accessible mode of transport. Yet in practice, the cycling mobility system is not as accessible to everyone (van der Kloof 2022; Balkmar 2020). The argument that not everyone has equal opportunities to cycle has been raised in several studies and by several actors. Steinbach and colleagues (2011) argue that the position of the cyclist is affected by class, ethnicity and gender as intersections ingrained with the social identity of the cyclist, most often masculine. As the U.S. activist group “the untokening.org” argues, there is a great risk in mobility advocacy that draws only upon the experiences of the most privileged, while marginalised groups’ experiences also need to be addressed to achieve sustainable and just cycling futures. Golub et al. (2016) note that it is also of importance to situate lived experiences of bicycling in the context of social inequalities related to gender, class and race. This is also what a just transition of the EU Green Deal is about. In short, without justice and inclusion effective and sustainable mobility transitions will not be reached.

1.2 Addressing behavioural change among disadvantaged groups

The contribution of ACCTING is to analyse how different interventions for cycling inclusion unfold on different groups, and with what effects on these peoples’ experienced gender+ inequalities. Among other measures, the study uses the idea of the cycling **ladder** (van der Kloof 2015) to capture participants’ cycling capacity and change therein before and after having taken part in an initiative. The ladder offers a way to analyse the extent to which initiatives manage to lower barriers to cycling for groups of intersectionally gendered people (see 1.3). Secondary change analysed is the extent to which the initiative supports social inclusion, breaking social isolation and other similar barriers.

To summarise, RL7 studies behavioural change across the following levels:

- At an **individual level**, using the three elements of cycling motility (access, competence and embrace; see section 1.3) to study behavioural change.
- At an **organisational level** by focusing on the initiative/organisation and in what ways it supports cycling inclusion (e.g., what they do, under what conditions and with what outcomes).
- At a **societal level**, examining the wider impacts that the initiatives can have at a general societal level, including the transport system more generally (e.g., other outcomes).

RL7 primarily focuses on the individual and organisational levels, although the societal and systemic levels are considered in the analyses through the concept of *Bikeability*, i.e. the hosting potential of the context to facilitate change or not (Schmassmann et al. 2024). As stated above, the cycle two research of RL7 *focuses on how cycling initiatives can help their participants to overcome barriers to cycling (or not), and what factors are important to make this happen*. It zooms in on their ways of organising, what they do, and the impact that such initiatives and programmes have on vulnerable groups/individuals to shift towards more sustainable transport (i.e., cycling).

Previous research on the processes and factors that make cycling attractive and achievable for disadvantaged groups suggests that different approaches are required than currently emphasised in cycling promotion campaigns (van der Kloof 2022). Information that builds solely on promoting the positive societal outcomes of cycling is often inadequate for achieving behavioural change since barriers for marginalised and disadvantaged groups are related to individual-level issues of health, knowledge, costs, lack of infrastructure, etc. (Carnevale et al. 2023; Zorell & Strid 2023). Concrete opportunities to learn new skills, overcome mental blocks, and access bikes are required (van der Kloof 2022; Bradley 2018). A framework offering an instrument to interpret the many initiatives to make the cycling mobility system more inclusive is the *Cycling participation ladder* (van der Kloof 2022).

The ladder is based on Vincent Kaufman’s concept of “motility” (Kaufman et al. 2004; Flamm and Kaufman, 2006). Motility is used to discuss *mobility potential* in relation to the activity locations that people can potentially reach. Hence, the motility of a person is the potential mobility this person has, determined by social inequalities and the geographical environment. Cycling as an everyday transport thus requires:

- Access to mobility resources such as suitable bikes, including access to resources relating to bike friendly infrastructure, economic resources and time.
- *Competence* as in skills to use the bike and ability to navigate in traffic, and
- *Embrace/Appropriation*³, as to what extent individuals, families or groups make use of the perceived or real access and competence to take up cycling in their everyday life (van der Kloof 2022). Embrace refers to values, motives and actual behaviour, and it is strongly linked to gender, age and ethnicity (van der Kloof 2015, 93).

The capacity to choose cycling for transportation is measured through these three elements, which are assumed to be prerequisites for behavioural change. Analysing these aspects in a framework of a person’s *cycling motility* (Hamidi 2023; Balkmar et al. 2025) provides further insight into how issues of inequality and differentiation are entangled with individual and group/families’ everyday mobilities, and it helps understand what barriers and enablers there are to cycling.

1.3 Case study selection and availability of initiatives

Building on the aforementioned insights, the RL7 study uses the concepts of access, competence and embrace to analyse the cycling capacity of individuals who participate in cycling initiatives *before and after the initiative took place* (see 3.2). Moreover, it analyses *what the initiatives do* to support individuals in overcoming barriers. This means that the initiatives studied in the research cycle represent *diverse* cases with the commonality that they all seek to improve cycling capacity (e.g. cycling motility) for marginalised or vulnerable groups through more than only information campaigns. Initiatives represented in the sample are:

- **Bike schools**, which teach participants (including participants with specific bodily challenges) how to ride a bike and improve their cycling competences.
- **Bike-to-school** initiatives, which support children, parents and volunteers to go by bike to school by facilitating a joint route. One of the bike-to-school initiatives we have studied also has a wider agenda, supporting pupils to get a deeper understanding of cycling and their broader environments/mobility needs.

³ van der Kloof (2022) suggests the concept embrace is more suitable than appropriation to refer to cycling in the context of practical interaction.

- **Bike kitchens**, which are communal bike repair shops that emphasise the importance of sharing ideas, problems and solutions to gain independence through bike knowledge and bike maintenance. The bike kitchens we have studied are of different kinds, a more activist driven initiative and those that use the bike kitchen format to support social inclusion in disadvantaged neighbourhoods.
- **Bike promotion** initiatives, which encourage the use of bikes as a means of everyday transportation, often by emphasising the positive aspects of cycling, such as being sustainable, affordable, healthy and a pleasant way of travelling. The initiatives selected do this through campaigns, organising social events, and by facilitating secure bike racks where cyclists can leave their bikes during school time.

The approach for studying bike initiatives – what they do and what impact they may have on participants' behavioural change – is based on a qualitative research design. The primary fieldwork consisted of (1) fieldwork observations, and (2) semi-structured interviews with participants, facilitators and potential participants in the bike initiatives, and/or other relevant informants involved in the initiative. Taken together, this research design allowed for developing an in-depth understanding of the initiatives (what they do), and the participants' background, reasons for taking part, and behavioural changes (if occurred).

In general, two case studies were analysed per country, with two exceptions due to availability. Greece focused on one case, while Sweden studied three cases. The main **selection criteria** for cases were:

- The cases should have the aim of stimulating the use of bikes by supporting behavioural change.
- The cases should either focus on vulnerable groups and/or vulnerable areas.
- A case should represent hands-on intervention(s) that produce (or have the potential to produce) a change in behaviour for people taking part in them.

There are differences in the *initiatives available* which met these criteria. Sweden, Belgium, Portugal and Italy studied initiatives such as bike schools, bike-to-school initiatives, and bike kitchens. Greece and Romania did not find these kinds of initiatives. Therefore, Greece focused on a bicycle organisation working with bike social events. Romania focused on initiatives that support cycling uptake through bike security (bike racks/bike security) and promotion campaigns for increased commuting by bike. The initiatives also reflect different forms of platforms, yet mainly NGOs and sports organisations.

The availability and variances of initiatives mirror the extent to which cycling is on the political agenda within the respective countries; part of wider pro-cycling policies; and the extent to which cycling is part of bottom-up initiatives' agendas. What binds the initiatives together is their contribution to *lower barriers* related to access, competence and embrace. The similarities and differences enrich the sample and enables the analysis of similarities, differences and overlaps in how the initiatives manage to support behavioural change among vulnerable groups and/or in disadvantaged areas across the case study contexts.

1.4 Case study contexts and target groups

A total of 12 case studies of initiatives have been carried out. Below follows a brief description of the contexts of the cases, their target groups, and the focus of each of the initiatives.

Belgium – bike school and bike-to-school

Belgium is a relatively bike-friendly country and has adequate-to-extensive cycling infrastructure. Flanders, where both Belgian case studies are located, has flat terrain, which means that cyclists can relatively easily get around.

General trends in Belgium indicate that women cycle slightly less than men. Older people also tend to make less use of bicycles than younger generations, although they are more willing to use electric bikes (Federale Overheidsdienst Mobiliteit en Vervoer, 2022). These same trends are reflected in the region of Flanders as well (Janssens, Ectors & Paul, 2023).

Case 1: De Fietsschool

De Fietsschool is a bike school initiative that teaches participants how to ride a bike and improves their cycling competences (i.e., cycling in traffic). This cycling initiative is likely the most prominent example of a bike school in Flanders that focuses on disadvantaged target groups like migrant women/girls, older people and people with low incomes. This initiative was selected for these reasons, and especially due to the focus on women and girls with migrant backgrounds. Women with a migrant background are heavily represented in the sample of (participant) interviews, which means ethnic, racial and/or social origin was also a relevant vulnerability dimension. Besides these, age and socioeconomic background are represented in the sample, intersecting with the aforementioned dimensions. Some participants also live in a more rural area. All interviewees, including facilitators, were women.

Bikeability context: The initiative operates in the municipalities of Leuven and Balen. The City of Leuven (100 000 inhabitants) is a quite a bike-friendly city, with various infrastructural provisions for cyclists like cycling streets, plenty of bicycle lanes, a partially car-free city centre, repair shops, parking areas, etc. The smaller and more rural municipality of Balen (population approximately 23 000) generally has a less-developed bike infrastructure and, although the big thoroughfares are outfitted with cycling lanes, they can still be somewhat dangerous to cyclists because of the busy and fast traffic (up to a legal maximum of 50km/h). In terms of nationality, the population of Leuven is more diverse than in Balen.

Case 2: School op de Teller

School op de Teller can be characterised as a bike-to-school initiative with unique features and characteristics. This initiative was chosen because of the innovative efforts it engages in to get pupils involved in cycling and their broader environments/mobility needs. The “School op de Teller” initiative (“Schools Count!”) provides a ready-made course to schools that helps pupils from the 4th, 5th and 6th grades (~10-12 years old) engage with topics of mobility around their schools and neighbourhood. This includes subjects such as the safety and overall impact of traffic in the area as well as the promotion of cycling, both in commuting to school and beyond commuting. The overall guiding principle is to encourage sustainable mobility, meaning that mobility is not only more climate-friendly but also more human-friendly. As part of the lessons, pupils learn to think about their environment in a novel way, coming up together with solutions for mobility issues.

While it can be categorised as a bike-to-school initiative, it is also more than that, potentially influencing a whole community to adopt safer and more sustainable modes of transport. No similar initiatives were found. Geography is a vulnerability, as the pupils that engage with this initiative primarily reside in rural areas. Age is another prominent vulnerability factor.

The initiative has been implemented in a number of different elementary schools across Flanders, but the specific iterations of this initiative that were researched are located in the City of Ghent and the submunicipalities⁴ of Zomergem and Baal.

Bikeability context: Like other bigger cities in Flanders, Ghent has an adequate cycling infrastructure consisting of interventions like cycling streets, plenty of bicycle lanes, repair shops, parking areas, etc. Rurally located, Zomergem has some cycling lanes and signage, but this does not seem sufficient as a significant number of streets do not have any. Moreover, the traffic situation is not entirely safe, with right-of-way and speed limits often not being respected. Likewise, the rural submunicipality of Baal has limited infrastructure. The larger city of Ghent (population approximately 265 000) has a younger and more diverse population than the more rural Zomergem and Baal. Bike ownership is high in all three areas but inhabitants in Ghent are far more likely to use bikes as their main mode of transport.

Greece – Bike promotion

There are not many cycling initiatives in Greece actively organising events. In fact, the Cycling Sports Association of Thessaloniki⁵ was the only initiative found that was active in organising some events. Due to difficulties finding relevant initiatives, only one case study was conducted in Greece.

The main modes of transport in the city are bus or car. A study in 2018 showed that, for commuting in the city, citizens choose cars over sustainable means of transportation (public transport, walking, cycling). More specifically, 44% of people chose the car, 11% a motorbike, a similar percentage moved on foot, while 27% chose the bus. Although specific cycling uptake numbers for Thessaloniki are not widely published, the emphasis on sustainable mobility aligns with European trends showing modest growth in urban cycling. EuroVelo data⁶ highlights increasing ridership on certain routes, including EuroVelo 11, which passes through Thessaloniki.

Case 3: Cycling Sports Association of Thessaloniki

Cycling Sports Association of Thessaloniki are a team that organises events aimed at the promotion of cycling (popular, mass and sports) and the principle of sustainable mobility. It comprises five active members and most of their actions take place in/near Thessaloniki. Most of their actions are bike schools, where citizens can learn how to bike safely in the urban setting of Thessaloniki. The initiative helps to improve competence and embrace in cycling, supporting participants' use of cycling as their main mode of mobility. The participants interviewed participated in the event "Sunday rides", when the group cycles specific routes in the city; some participants also had taken part in the initiatives' "Safe cycling courses". To be able to take part, the participants needed to know how to cycle, the initiative supported them to improve confidence in cycling in the city.

The initiative also organises activities at schools, like talks and 'learning how to bike' activities. Moreover, they consult local authorities on biking matters in the city. Almost all ten research participants in this case were women. Another prominent vulnerability factor is low socio-economic

⁴ Submunicipalities are an administrative division in Belgium that refers to former municipalities that were merged into one bigger municipality. Decision-making happens at the level of the municipality.

⁵ The municipality of Thessaloniki has approximately 319 000 inhabitants, population in the wider metropolitan area is considerably higher. 92.22% of the population of the municipality of Thessaloniki are Greek nationals, while 7.78% have foreign citizenship. Of these, only 15.41% come from EU countries, while the remaining 84.59% come from other countries or do not have citizenship. In 2022, the unemployment rate in Thessaloniki was 25.8% and in the wider region Central Macedonia, 23.8% of residents were at risk of poverty.

⁶https://pro.eurovelo.com/news/2024-10-22_cycling-counts-in-europe-numbers-from-the-eurovelo-usage-barometer-show-stability-for-2024.

status. Single mothers were also interviewed. In addition, one participant mentioned mental health issues, and one person has gone through consistent treatment for a serious medical condition.

Bikeability context: There are very few bike lanes in Thessaloniki and some of the existing ones are poorly maintained. The Municipality of Thessaloniki has not launched any specific plans or actions for ensuring equity in cycling and there is almost no planning for bikes in general. However, in their effort to upgrade the quality of life for its residents and introduce the city of Thessaloniki to the list of the most sustainable urban European cities, the city is preparing a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) in collaboration with the Institute of Sustainable Mobility and Transport Networks (IMET) of the National Center for Research and Technological Development (EKETA). Alternative means of transportation (use of public transport, walking and cycling) are promoted through the SUMP, which potentially will lead to an increase in the level of safety provided to all commuters, a reduction in environmental pollution, and an overall upgrade of the quality of the city network.

Italy – bike-to-school and bike kitchen

At the time of this study, the main policy to promote cycling at urban, regional and/or national level is the "General Plan of Bicycle Mobility (PGMC)", which was launched in 2021 and covers three years (2022-2024). The plan sets out measures for the progressive implementation of the National Cycle Network, including budget allocations and annual targets. It also outlines ways to integrate cycling with road, rail and public transport systems, and measures to improve safety.

In Rome, 60% of the population travels by private car (46% in 2019) and only 9.8% of the population chooses public transport (15% in 2019). Cycling seems to play an important role in *future mobility* plans. This is reflected in the amount of funding allocated to cycling for the next few years, which is about 49 million euros (PNRR and Jubilee funds). According to the local authorities, this budget will be used to improve or create 15 cycle routes, totalling around 55 kilometres of city-wide cycle routes.

In 2021, the Municipality of Rome adopted the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) that aims to link mobility policies and infrastructure interventions with economic, social, urban and environmental strategies. Within the SUMP there is a specific cycling mobility programme, the "Biciplan". Its aim is to define actions to promote and intensify the use of the bicycle as a means of transport (both for daily needs and for tourism and recreation) and to improve the safety of cyclists and pedestrians by creating a high-quality active mobility infrastructure and drawing up an ad hoc plan to guide its development. As for the general plan, no documents or announcements are available from 2021 onwards.

Although the number of people cycling has increased in Rome during recent years, in both districts of the initiatives the majority use bicycles as a hobby and not as a means of transport. Bicycle use is associated with people from the middle and upper social classes who are highly motivated to sustainable mobility. The age of typical cyclists is between 30 and 50 years and they are usually Italian or European people of both genders. Apart from them, it is people with immigrant background from other continents who cycle for work as riders for delivery companies. In this category, women are almost non-existent, and the vast majority are young immigrant men without disabilities from a low socio-economic background.

Case 4: Bike-to-school Rome

'Bike-to-school' is a demonstration action and spontaneous movement of children, parents and volunteers. Since 2013, on the last Friday of the month, the initiative has enabled children to cycle to several schools in Rome. The initiative is part of a wider campaign, the Clean Cities Campaign, run by a European coalition of organisations committed to promoting "Street for Kids" and "Bike-to-school" initiatives at local level. The events are organised via WhatsApp chats for schools and classes.

Anyone with a bike can join the meeting points and then cycle together to school. The initiative is entirely run by parents, mostly aged between 40 and 50.

The participants in the initiative are in general people experiencing geographical, socio-economic or political/ideological vulnerabilities. Within Municipality V, the primary school where the Bike-to-school activity studied takes place is located on the border between two multicultural and working-class urban areas: Tor Pignattara and Casilino⁷.

Bikeability context: The bicycle infrastructure in Rome needs to be improved, especially in the two Italian case study areas. The infrastructure conditions for cycling in the Tor Pignattara district (Case 4) are not good and there have been fatal accidents of cyclists. The roads leading from the bike-to-school meeting points to the school have no safe cycle lanes. There is a bike lane in the area that is half a metre wide and has no kerb. Cycle lanes are sometimes hindered by parked cars and waste bins being placed in the way.

Case 5: Bike kitchen CICLOFFICINA

The Bike kitchen initiative is a cycle workshop called CICLOFFICINA . It is in Rome on the premises of a building that has been squatted for about 20 years by multiple families from different migrant backgrounds and living in precarious socio-economic situations. The residents in the squatted building can be considered vulnerable due to the geographical and socio-economic conditions in which they live. Those who participate in the Ciclofficina stress they experience vulnerabilities also related to the political/ideological dimensions of being a cyclist in a city adverse to sustainable mobility (IT07, IT08). The occupied building is located in a district within the Municipality of Rome VIII. It is a central neighbourhood and well served by rail transport. It has no specific socio-economic problems and is home to several company headquarters and university buildings.

Bikeability context: The bike infrastructure in the area is not particularly safe for cyclists. In recent years, a large road through the neighbourhood had been identified by the local administration as the route for a 2 km cycle path, with the aim of encouraging people to cycle regularly. However, following complaints from businesses and residents in the area, work was halted and there are currently no plans to complete the project. Thus, the infrastructure works have remained limited to a short cycle lane that does not connect to other cycle paths in the city and neighbourhood.

Portugal – Bike kitchens

The percentage of bicycle users in Lisbon remains very small, although it has seen some growth in recent years. According to the 2021 population census, only 1.34% of the population uses a bicycle as their primary means of transportation to work or study, with the figure dropping to just 0.75% among women. In the Marvila area and in the Carnide parish, the proportion of people using bicycles as their main mode of transport is even lower, at 0.54% and 0.93% respectively. The primary users of bicycles in these areas are young men, typically between the ages of 18 and 40.

⁷ The former is a large neighbourhood with a high percentage of foreigners of different nationalities and a social hardship/deprivation index measuring socio-occupational criticality of 1.1, while Casilino is much less densely populated and has a higher social hardship/deprivation index of 2.7. The latter is different since in recent years Tor Pignattara has undergone progressive gentrification, because of which many professionals have moved to the neighbourhood.

Case 6: CICLOPES

The main goal of the project CICLOPES – Achata Colinas (Flatten Hills) is to promote the use of bicycles in disadvantaged neighbourhoods in Lisbon. The main targets are young people, especially from low-income groups and immigrants. The initiative promotes the following activities:

- Cycle workshop – bike repair service for those unable to pay repair costs.
- Donation of bicycles to young people who do not have access to bikes (anyone can donate a bike to the project).
- Kids and teenagers learn how to repair bikes and are able to use the bikes they repair.
- Cycling lessons in schools and in Ciclo-oficinas / Cycling Workshops.
- Bike tours.

The initiative's primary focus extends beyond simply encouraging the use of bikes. It emphasises social inclusion, empowerment, education and sustainable mobility. The initiative moreover facilitates access to bicycles by allowing community members to borrow a limited number of bikes at no cost. However, children and young people under 18 require parental permission to use the community bicycles, which restricts access, particularly for those children whose parents are frequently absent.

Case 7: PRODAC Social Promotion Centre

The Bike Kitchen at the PRODAC Social Promotion Centre (Centro de Promoção Social da PRODAC) promotes cycling inclusion by making bicycles accessible to groups who may otherwise have limited access. The cycling workshop operates as a collaborative space where community members can learn to repair and maintain their bicycles. The PRODAC Social Promotion Centre, in collaboration with other local partners, has actively promoted several initiatives to encourage everyday bicycle use, including “Bicicletas com Asas” (Bicycles with Wings) – A small-scale project aimed at providing bicycles to socially disadvantaged individuals, particularly those unable to afford one, such as vulnerable youth, migrants and refugees – and “Bicicleta para Todos” (Bicycle for All) which provides adapted bicycles for people with reduced mobility. PRODAC also organises bicycle rides with children and youth from the PRODAC neighbourhood and nearby areas.

The participants in both initiatives are in general people with no particular vulnerabilities other than socio-economic, yet some of them have an immigrant background or belong to the Roma community. All neighbourhoods included in the study, share similar socio-economic challenges, including high levels of unemployment, low-income households, and social exclusion. These areas are heavily reliant on social housing, and residents often face difficulties related to education, employment and access to services.

Bikeability context: The use of bicycles as a mode of transport in Lisbon and particularly in the case study areas, is very low. This fact is due to several factors, which were also referred to in the interviews and in the “Report of the Participatory Study on Mobility in Marvila” (Relatório do Estudo Participativo sobre a Mobilidade em Marvila). These factors include lacking competence to use bikes, especially among women and older people; the absence of adequate cycling infrastructure and safety concerns; as well as topography, socio-economic and cultural factors hindering cycling. Neither of the two study areas has adequate cycling infrastructure, which discourages residents from using bicycles as a mode of transport.

Romania – Bike promotion

The Romanian case study context is Iasi, the third largest city in Romania (population of 271 692). Generally, men tend to cycle there more frequently than women, both in the city of Iasi and in the

outskirts of it (nearby forests, practicing mountain biking). The Alliance for Promoting Alternative Transportation (APTA) in Iasi advocates for improving cycling infrastructure, and it promotes cycling as a safe and accessible mode of transportation to encourage more women to cycle. There is no dedicated support for cycling from local/national authorities.

The initiatives chosen were the active ones in Iasi, whose aims tap into the general objective of the project. There were difficulties in identifying initiatives that have vulnerable individuals as described in the project as target population, since the biking culture in Romania is not extensive or vibrant.

Case 8: 'Green zone for bikes'

The 'Green zone for bikes' is an initiative which focuses on installing bike racks in two high schools in Iasi. Since 2022, an IT company together with the local community has installed covered bike racks at two high schools within two neighbourhoods in Iasi. Thereby, the initiative offers students, employees of the schools, and the wider community in the neighbourhood access to covered and safe bike racks where they can leave their bikes.

Case 9: 'Bike2school/work/shop'

'Bike2school/work/shop' is an initiative that encourages participants to use cycling as a means of transport in Iasi. The initiative promotes biking through social media platforms, press releases, participating in decision-making conferences on alternative ways of transportation in the city, and it participates in actions and activities meant to encourage young people to bike (such as installing bike racks in schools).

In the general sample, gender, age, migrant status and economic situation are the main vulnerabilities represented. There seems to be a balance between the number of participants from marginalised and disadvantaged groups.

Bikeability context: Even though the geographical conditions would be suitable for cycling, the car norm remains strong in Iasi. The infrastructure conditions for cycling in Iasi is deficient – there is few or non-existent cycling infrastructure in place. On paper, it appears to be more than 40 km of dedicated bike lanes, but the bike lanes are in fact most often sidewalks for walking. Also, the materials used and the connectivity between bike lanes is neither properly done nor well-signalled.

Sweden – Bike schools

In current Swedish planning and policy discourse, cycling is seen as efficient commuting and a key component in advancing more sustainable transport. Yet on a national level, with some regional exceptions, cycling has declined in Sweden (van der Meulen and Mukhtar-Landgren, 2021). It is primarily the more affluent quarter of Swedish citizens that cycles, and the less affluent quarter that does not (Eriksson et al., 2022, p. 57). Cycling among foreign-born in Sweden has previously been described as relatively low compared with Swedes in general, explained with reference to a combination of "good bus communications" in the suburbs, where many groups of foreign-born live, a "weak cycling culture", and their origin "from countries with weak cycling cultures" (Trivector, 2014, our translation).

The three initiatives studied in Sweden are bike schools with different target groups, including seniors, disabled and women with immigrant background. The bike school for seniors stands out as probably being one of a kind.

Case 10 and 11: 'The tricycle bike school' for seniors and paracyclists

The 'tricycle bike school' is a cycling club that conducts training/try-on cycling indoors in the athletics arena in a Swedish middle-sized city. The initiative targets two groups: Seniors (case 10), and

disabled people (case 11), but not any specific socio-economic groups nor neighbourhoods. The participants are marginalised because of their age and bodily disabilities and combinations thereof. They come from different areas with different socio-economic conditions. Beginners are introduced to tricycling and carefully taken care of, often supported around the track to familiarise them with the tricycle and balance. In case 10, the first hour of the practice is divided into warm up and cycling around the track, and the second hour is dedicated to having coffee together and socialising. Shorter informational presentations occur during coffee break, often with a focus on balancing training and traffic safety issues. In case 11, the tricycle bike school paracycling section is devoted to indoor/outdoor cycling practice/training. There is no specific time to sit down and have coffee/socialising. Instead, the focus is more on individual cycling practice. The aim of both schools is to support those who have a mobility or visual impairment and want to be able to ride a bike. The initiative also facilitates different kinds of tricycles, which works well for neurologically or muscularly impaired bodies.

The selection of participants in these initiatives was restricted to those participants who took part in the specific events, most often ethnic Swedes, which in turn biased the sample towards people with Swedish background. A third bike school has also been studied, targeting women with immigrant background, representing great diversity in terms of ethnic backgrounds.

Case 12: 'The bike school for women'

'The bike school for women' cycling school is part of an international NGO, which currently runs three bike schools in different disadvantaged neighbourhoods in a middle-sized city in Sweden. The vulnerability factors among the participants are their gender, ethnicity and socio-economic conditions. The initiative offers a cycling school during five weeks in the three different disadvantaged areas. Moreover, the school offers supervised cycling training in safe spaces, following a multiple step programme.

Bikeability context: The Swedish case study sites present well-developed cycling infrastructure. The middle-sized cities where the initiatives work (approximately 160 000 residents) have a well-developed cycling path network and actively support cycling to increase its mobility share. The studied cities are so called 'cycling cities' which is a label used to stress that the city geography and infrastructure are suitable and supportive of cycling. Cycling in both cities is considered 'normal', i.e. there is a plurality of cyclists across age, gender and ethnicities. Yet, this holds true to a much more limited extent for disabled persons, including seniors using tricycles.

1.5 Summary of the case studies

In sum, RL7 focuses on cycling initiatives for change, with particular emphasis on inclusion and how to increase diverse users' capacity to cycle. A total of 12 initiatives are studied:

- Bike schools (N=4) targeting seniors, people with disabilities, women with immigrant backgrounds (SE, BE)
- Bike-to-school (N=2) targeting children, parents, and students/citizens (BE, IT)
- Bike kitchens (N=3) targeting young people living in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas and cyclists in general (IT, PT)
- Bike promotion (N=3) targeting women living under poor socioeconomic conditions, citizens more generally (EL, RO) and students in particular (RO)

The vulnerabilities targeted are intersections of gender, age, bodily ability, socioeconomic status and geographical location. Barriers related to real or perceived safety are addressed, mainly how differently situated cycling bodies experience cycling (un)safety.

There are great differences in bikeability across the different case study sites, with Sweden and Belgium representing more cycling friendly infrastructures compared to the cases of Romania, Greece, Italy and Portugal. This suggests great varieties in the *hosting potential of the context to facilitate change*.

2. Methodology and study materials

2.1 Choice of methods and strategies for recruitment

RL7 aims to examine the effects of bike initiatives on participants' behaviour. Specifically, it assesses what bike initiatives do and what impact they can have on achieving participants to change their cycling behaviour. With the focus on behavioural change, the RL7 team anticipated it was likely for change to occur in various ways depending on the initiative and its target groups. The methodological approach has been the same across all research sites, except for when an initiative focuses on younger people (BE, PT), which required slightly different measures (questionnaire, group interviews). Some initiatives, like the bike schools for seniors and disabled people, was ongoing over several years, while other initiatives, such as bike schools for immigrant women, took place for a limited time. Therefore, to account for change evoked by the initiative (including non-change), it was agreed that interviews with participants could take place while the initiative was ongoing or afterwards. There are limitations to this approach, as the study can only capture behavioural change based on what the research participants say and based on their understanding of how the initiative impacted their cycling potential. To fully address their long-term impacts and transformative potential, a longitudinal approach and more diverse data sources would be more suitable.

The selected approach for studying change in behaviour is **qualitative research**. The fieldwork consisted of a combination of 1) fieldwork observations as part of an ethnographically informed research methodology; and 2) interviews with participants and trainers/facilitators active in the initiatives, and/or other relevant informants involved in the initiatives. The research design had as its goal to contribute with an in-depth understanding of cycling barriers and enablers impacting the ACCTING target groups. A starting point is the need to question the linear causal assumptions behind cycling promotion, for example, the hypothesis that simply informing about the psycho-physical benefits of cycling will get more families and youth to cycle (Silonsaari, 2025). A qualitative approach makes it possible to study the cycling promotion initiatives in their specific socio-spatial contexts to gain a deeper understanding of the combined impacts of, for example, social support from family, friends and local communities, the perceived 'bikeability' of participants' everyday environments, their (lack of) access to bikes and (in)capacity to cycle and the impacts of social infrastructure to support cycling (Silonsaari, 2025, 8).

Previous studies on everyday mobilities in disadvantaged neighbourhoods and marginalised communities have addressed difficulties recruiting research participants. Joelsson et al. (2024) have pointed to difficulties related to language skills (both researchers and research participants), research participants' lack of trust in research institutions, and that research is confused with governments and surveillance. Against this background, a reason for this research design was that it enabled **recruitment and gaining trust** with potential informants and groups who usually do not participate in research and whose experiences is less visible, both in research and in the public discussion about everyday mobility (Joelsson, et al., 2024). To overcome recruitment challenges, all partners used facilitators or organisers of the various initiatives as mediators to establish trust with participants and recruitment. Some also reported spending considerable amount of time on site to establish trust and facilitate recruitment.

Observations are committed to first-hand experience and the study of a particular cultural or social setting. It means that the researchers immerse themselves in the activities, which is important to gain a deeper understanding of the case and the participants' perspectives. To recruit *potential* participants, partners approached and interviewed people present during the opening hours of

initiatives (bike kitchens), people who were likely to take part over time (seniors who helped their partners to cycle), or bystanders of initiatives (bike-to-school). In this way, partners made sure that the non-participants interviewed were all people who knew about the initiatives but for various reasons did not participate.

The research design thereby allowed for flexible arrangements to meet recruitment challenges. For example, the Portuguese team performed collective group interviews with children and young adults taking part in the initiatives (Case 6 and 7). This way they could recruit interviewees to participate in ways that suited them, and to provide further insights on the impact of behavioural change that the initiatives had. By contrast to a survey or other quantitative measures, the qualitative approach was used with the goal of reaching such under-represented groups and for opening up the possibility of asking questions not only through interviews, but also while the research participants took part in the initiative.

We anticipated approximately **7-8 interviews** per case, divided as follows:

- 4 interviews with participants of the initiative. Participants should take part in the initiative (or have been taking part). If possible, preferably of different ages, ethnicities, genders, (dis)abilities/functional variations, family constellations, occupations, etc.
- 2-3 interviews with trainers, facilitators, key persons, representatives active in the initiative. Interview in combination with field-talks. Expert interviews with someone from the municipality or other relevant organisation that can provide a 'macro-perspective' on the case could be included if relevant.
- 1-2 interviews with non-participants. Interviews with people that would be part of the target group, but who do not engage/participate in the initiative. The aim was to understand their reasons for not participating. With them, only interviews were to be conducted.

Most national teams met this goal. However, there are variations depending on availability of initiatives (EL, who focused on one case but completing more interviews) and age composition of participants (PT, who did group interviews).

The material collected is comprised of the interviews, field notes from taking part in the activities arranged by the initiatives, and additional documents that could help understand the activities. To this end, online websites were used if available (which was the case in SE, BE, IT). In addition, we consulted data from statistical bureaus and public administrations for socioeconomic data on the studied neighbourhoods and on transport context. The Belgian team also used anonymous questionnaires that the teachers of the initiatives handed out in their classes (case 2) to evaluate the course. However, the outcome was thin, so no additional findings were added through this approach.

2.2 Tools for fieldwork

Several fieldwork tools were produced to support harmonised data collection across the sites:

- A research design guideline providing an introduction to the field of cycling research from a gender+ intersectionality perspective, outlining the chosen methodology and previous research relevant for RL7 RC2.
- A desk research template.
- A fieldwork log template.
- RL7 information leaflet to be handed out to potential participants. A sample consent form was provided by the Swedish team. Each team provided their own consent forms based in regional/national requirements.

- Fieldwork guidelines describing the analytical framework, description of outcomes studied, instructions on how to collect data with a particular focus on interviewing and fieldwork ethics and reporting.
- Interview grids for a) facilitators and b) participants and potential/non-participants.
- Interview reporting grids for a) facilitators and b) participants.
- National reporting grid.

All study materials had been discussed and updated accordingly with the RL7 team to ensure harmonised data collection.

The gender+ intersectionality dimensions addressed in the RL were based on previous research and addressed through **explicit questions** (i.e., how common is diversity in cycling where the informant lives; is there diversity in staff; how is cycling diversity supported by the initiative; the extent in which the initiative managed to reach vulnerable groups or not). Gender+ intersectionality was also explored through questions that shed light on **wider gender dynamics** related to cycling and support for cycling inclusion, for example:

- To what extent embodied experiences of cycling impacted their cycling capacity across intersections of gender, age, bodily ability, socioeconomic status and geographical location.
- To what extent the research participants' dependences, vulnerabilities and care relations had effects on their cycling ability in everyday life.
- To what extent vulnerabilities and experiences of (un)safety impacted on their ability to embrace cycling within the cycling initiative and in everyday life.
- The extent in which gender+ intersectionality mattered for participating in the initiative, to what extent diversity in staff was important to the participant.

2.3 Ethical issues

Depending on national context and the nature of the partner institution in question, ethical approval was not always needed (i.e. Belgium and Italian teams). However, in countries where it was required, partners obtained ethical approval from relevant authorities before conducting interviews.

Prior to the interviews, confidentiality and pseudonymisation of the data were assured. All participants were informed about the purpose of the project and given information about how and what data should be collected and how it should be stored. Recordings and transcripts were to be securely stored at each partner institution. In the interview reports shared with other partners, data is anonymised, and pseudonyms are used. Consent forms were either signed or, in the case of online interviews, given verbally and recorded.

Few reported their own positionality as a hinder, but in two cases (Belgium and Italy) language barriers presented a hinder to conducting some interviews. All partners reported using facilitators or organisers of the various initiatives as mediators to establish trust with participants. Some also reported spending considerable amount of time on site to establish trust. The Swedish researcher, for example, participated in most meetings with the groups for case 10 (seniors), where he also helped with practical issues and engaged in small talks during field work. The same researcher also stressed the importance of engaging in the interviews with an open mindset, asking the participant to share their narrative on their own terms. Age was carefully considered as some older participants needed longer time to respond. Disability mattered in the sense that some participants had helpers (parent, employed assistant) who sometimes filled in during interviews. The interviewer primarily addressed (with speech and eye contact) the interviewed person and not the helper.

Only the Portuguese partners reported issues in obtaining informed consent. An additional challenge in their cases was that the initiatives selected had children and teenagers as their main target groups. As most potential participants were under 18 years old, participation required parental consent (which was collected). Contacting the parents was challenging because many of the children and young people targeted lack adequate parental support and are often left to fend for themselves. For this reason, contact with the parents was made indirectly through local institutions that promoted or partnered with the initiatives. Consequently, the interviews were conducted collectively and in the presence of staff members from these institutions. This approach had potential implications for comparability since individual narratives were not collected. Despite these limitations, the interviews with participants (three group interviews) and facilitators (who possessed in-depth knowledge about the participants and the social and territorial challenges in the neighbourhood), in combination with the ethnographic approach and use of 'mobile methods' (i.e. cycling with the informants and participation in everyday activities), provided a very rich data set.

The study has focused on changed behaviour and the impacts that the studied initiatives have had on individuals' capacity to cycle. Yet, the study has foremost been able to capture participants' intentions to change, which is a limitation of the study. The study has not been able to capture long-term impacts which the initiatives may have, which limits the ability to fully assess the initiatives' transformative potential.

Furthermore, the qualitative approach has enabled establishing trust, which in turn was essential for recruiting the targeted marginalised and vulnerable groups. It also allowed gaining an in-depth understanding of specific initiatives and their participants. Nevertheless, it also comes with the limitation that broader trends and patterns may have been overlooked.

3. Collected data and analysis

This section briefly presents the different steps of data collection and the types of data gathered. The steps and timeframe for data collection is summarised in table 1, outlining the process of identifying and selecting initiatives for the second research cycle. Most teams were able to follow the timeframe, but due to difficulties finding initiatives and informants, some teams required more time to finalise their fieldwork.

Table 1: Time frame for data collection

Action	Time frame
Desk research for the identification of initiatives	May/Aug 2023 (M16-M19)
Collective decisions about initiatives and sites	September 2023 (M20)
Collection and analysis of contextual data and data about the initiatives and context, establishing contacts	September/October 2023 (M20/M21)
Preparation for fieldwork: participant observations, interview grids etc.	September/November 2023 (M20/M22)
Fieldwork	October 2023/April 2024 (M21/M27)
Country-level reporting	July 2024 (M30)
RL-level reporting	September 2024 (M32)

3.1 Case studies and barriers addressed

As mentioned in 1.3, despite differences in how the initiatives approach barriers to cycling for vulnerable and marginalised groups, their common denominator is their ambition to lower key barriers to cycling across:

- Barriers related to **competence** is about the ability to use bikes. Initiatives such as bike schools, bike-to-school actions and bike kitchens aim to lower barriers related to competence in cycling and participants' ability to take care of and fix their bikes.
- Barriers related to **access** encompass bikes and infrastructure suitable for one's needs. Initiatives such as bike kitchens, bike-to-school actions and bike racks lower access barriers.
- Barriers related to **embrace** is about to what extent individuals, families or groups make use of the perceived or real *access* and *competence* to take up cycling in their everyday life (van der Kloof, 2022). Examples of initiatives that support embrace primarily include bike promotion initiatives that target women, socioeconomically disadvantaged groups, etc., who know how to cycle and have access to bikes.

The following section specifies which initiatives address which of these key barriers. Some initiatives address a combination of barriers.

Table 2: Barriers addressed per initiative

Competence	
Bike school	De Fietsschool (Case 1) and Bike school women (Case 12) both address immigrant women. Socioeconomic, ethnic, racial and/or social vulnerabilities. (BE)
	The Tricycle school seniors (Case 10) targets old(er) age seniors. Rather homogenic ethnic Swedish backgrounds, although with socioeconomic differences in the sample. (SE)
	The Tricycle school disabled (Case 11) targets disabled persons of different gender and ages. (SE)
Bike-to-school	School op de Teller (Case 2) is a bike-to-school initiative and more, targeting school children. (BE)
	Bike-to-school Rome (Case 4) targets children and parents to support cycling to school. (IT)
Competence and Access	
Bike kitchens	Ciclofficina bike kitchen (Case 5) primarily promotes access and competence in bicycle repair skills for cyclists in Rome. (IT)
	Ciclopes bike kitchen (Case 6) facilitates access and competence in bikes for young people living in socioeconomically disadvantaged neighbourhoods in Lisbon. (PT)
	PRODAC Social Promotion Centre (Case 7) targets young people living in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas in Lisbon. (PT)
Embrace and access	
Bike promotion	Cycling Sports Association (Case 3) targets women living under poor socioeconomic conditions and other vulnerabilities to take up cycling for their everyday transport needs. (EL)
	Green zone for bikes (Case 8) installs bike racks at schools to support students to take up cycling. (RO)
	Bike2school/work/shop (Case 9) targets the citizens of Iasi more generally to support cycling to school, work and shop. (RO)

The vulnerabilities represented in the cases reflect intersections of gender, age, physical ability, socioeconomic status and geographical location. Participants in the bike schools present an interesting cluster of cases that can be further contrasted with each other to shed light on intersectionality.

3.2 Measurements

To measure the degree to which the initiatives contribute to behavioural change, the participants were asked to reflect upon their cycling capacity before and after taking part in the initiative. For example: Before the bike initiative, how would you say your ability to ride a bike was? Can you describe to me how the initiative has supported you in cycling/access to bikes? Are there any specific barriers that the initiative helped you overcome?

- To measure changes in the cycling **competence** of participants, the teams inquired the research participants' level of cycling skill before and after taking part in the initiative. Informants were asked to choose between "not able to cycle", "able to cycle within the initiative"⁸, "able to cycle in park", "able to cycle in traffic". Additional questions were asked about specific situations that are more demanding than others, for example, traffic situations and if cycling with children is avoided or not.
- To measure changes in **access** to bikes before and after taking part in an initiative, the informants were asked if they had access to a suitable *bike* that fits the person's needs. Further questions were raised about the ways that the initiative changed anything with regards to this. Participants were asked to score access: "No access to bike", "bike unfit to needs", "bike fit to needs".
- To measure changes in **embrace**⁹, the informants were asked whether the initiative had made the person change to identify as a cyclist or not, if they own a bike, plan on getting a bike and go cycling on a regular basis. The combined responses were scored as either a "weak embrace", "medium embrace", or "strong embrace".
- Additional questions were asked **about behavioural change and intentions to change**: After the initiative, do you usually cycle? Do you intend to cycle more? Tell me more, where, with whom, under what conditions? Do you own a bike, plan on getting a bike and go cycling on a regular basis? Did participating in the initiative make you change (or not)? What would make you continue cycling?

⁸ To be able to cycle 'within the initiative' refers to the initiative as a whole, which includes other activities promoted by the association within the school. If only the bike to school initiative is considered, the result indicates that the children improved their cycling and felt more comfortable cycling in the streets/traffic. To participate in the bike to school initiative, everyone had to be able to ride a bike.

⁹ "Embrace is about making the cycling system yours, mastering cycling, feeling positive about it, knowing that cycling fits with your identity and image and having reasons to ride and destinations to ride to." Please make an estimation based on how the informant responds.

3.3 Sample statistics

Most teams met the target number of interviews in each of the categories outlined in section 2.1. However, as seen in table 3, there are variations depending on availability of initiatives. In case 2 (Belgium), the initiative targeted school children. By contrast to the Portuguese case where the participants were older and consent was obtained from their parents, the children in the Belgian case was too young to be interviewed, therefore the team focused on additional facilitator interviews.

Table 3: Number of participants per case and country.

Country	Case	Participants	Non-participants	Facilitators
Belgium	Case 1	4	1	2
	Case 2	-	-	5
Greece	Case 3	10	-	1
Italy	Case 4	4	2	3
	Case 5	4	2	2
Portugal	Case 6	1 (+1 group)	2	5
	Case 7	1 (+ 2 group)	-	1
Romania	Case 8	4	1	2
	Case 9	4	1	1
Sweden	Case 10	7	-	3
	Case 11	4	-	1
	Case 12	4	-	4
Total		47	9	30

In total, 86 individuals have been interviewed. In addition, 3 group interviews encompassing a total of 30 young people aged 10-16 years were conducted in the Portuguese case studies. Table 4 presents the sample statistics of the **participants** and **non-participants** in the RL case studies based on the overarching demographic assessment used for the second research cycle. The table also shows the distribution per country. Sample statistics per initiative from a gender+ intersectionality perspective will be presented in the subsequent section.

Group interviewees and **facilitators** are not included in the table. For facilitators, only age and gender were systematically collected. Out of 30 facilitators interviewed, 18 (60%) were women. They ranged in age between 21 and 78 years but two-thirds were in the 30-49 years age bracket.

In general, the sample represents more participants categorised as women than men. We can only speculate how this mirrors the extent to which women have a greater need, interest, and find the opportunities to participate in initiatives that support cycling. Research shows that, in general, women are less likely to cycle, often because of concerns with traffic safety, lack of adequate cycling infrastructure or social safety (Xie and Spinney, 2018).

The table above includes both participants (N=47) and non-participants (N=9). Considering the low number of non-participants, it is not possible to draw any general conclusions about the difference between these two categories. As several of the standardised questions were added after fieldwork had commenced, no answer was recorded in some cases. ‘Care responsibility’ is one such late addition where the ‘yes’ responses could potentially be higher. As this was an open question, it could also have been left blank because there was no care responsibilities indicated. For those that did indicate such responsibilities, seventeen mentioned children and two indicated caring for a partner. The children ranged in aged between five months and 24 years.

Table 4: Participants and non-participants demographics

		SE	BE	GR	IT	RO	PT	Total
Gender	Woman	14	5	9	8	7	3	82% (46)
	Man	1	-	1	4	3	1	18% (10)
Age	18-29	4	-	3	2	7	1	30% (17)
	30-49	2	2	4	9	2	1	36% (20)
	50-64	1	3	2	1	1	2	18% (10)
	65-84	8	-	1	-	-	-	16% (9)
Geography	Big city	-	2	10	11	10	4	66% (37)
	Suburb	1	-	-	1	-	-	4% (2)
	Town/small city	14	1	-	-	-	-	27% (15)
	Village	-	2	-	-	-	-	4% (2)
National background	Born in country	11	-	9	10	6	4	71% (40)
	Born abroad	4	5	1	2	4	-	29% (16)
Education	Elementary school or less	1	-	1	-	-	4	11% (6)
	Secondary school	2	1	5	4	4	-	29% (16)
	University/Professional training	1	4	4	7	6	-	39% (22)
	Not asked/no answer	11	-	-	1	-	-	21% (12)
Income	Comfortable	-	2	1	3	2	-	14% (8)
	Coping	1	1	4	6	3	2	30% (17)
	Difficult/very difficult	-	1	4	1	5	2	24% (13)
	Not asked/no answer	14	1	1	2	-	-	32% (18)
Occupation	Full-time work	-	-	4	6	3	2	27% (15)
	Part-time work	1	2	2	5	3	1	25% (14)
	Retired	9	1	1	-	-	-	20% (11)
	In education	3	-	1	-	4	-	14% (8)

	Unemployed	-	1	2	-	-	1	7% (4)
	Housework/care work	1	-	-	1	-	-	4% (2)
	Not asked/no answer	1	1	-	-	-	-	4% (2)
Disability/ health	Yes	10	1	4	-	4	1	36% (20)
	No	4	4	6	12	6	3	63% (35)
	Not asked	1	-	-	-	-	-	2% (1)
Care responsibility	Yes (children or partner)	4	2	4	6	3	-	34% (19)
	Not asked/not applicable	11	3	6	6	7	4	66% (37)

Differences between countries reflect the kind of initiatives each country covered. For example, most participants were born in their country of residence. However, in the bike schools in Sweden and Belgium aimed at migrant women (case 1 and 12), all participants were born abroad. A disability/health concern was indicated for all participants in the Swedish tricycle initiatives (case 10 and 11), but it was also quite common in cases 3 and 8. While the overall sample covers a range of ages, there are some national variations. Sweden has a higher average age as one of the initiatives was aimed at seniors (case 10) and Romania has a low average age as one of the initiatives focused on the installation of bike racks at schools (case 8). These age differences are also reflected in employment status, as older people tend to be retired and the youngest tend to be in education. The Italian cases reported some difficulties reaching the most vulnerable, and the participants interviewed also have a higher education and are more likely to live comfortably on present income than average.

Finally, the Portuguese cases included three group interviews with children. Two of these were more formalised interviews and one was a more informal conversation during a bike ride. In case 6, five boys and four girls aged between 11 and 16 years took part in the group interview. In case 7, two girls and three boys aged between 11 and 13 years took part in the interview, and approximately 15 children aged 10 to 14 participated in the bike ride. Individual level data is not available for these interviews, but all children were reported to be from low-income families. Unlike all other cases, where women by far outnumber men, these group interviews included slightly more boys than girls. The interviewees also indicated that this was the general pattern in the bike initiatives: more boys than girls took part.

Results

4. Results

4.1 Aggregated summary of impacts

This section outlines an aggregated summary of impacts that the initiatives had across the three key barriers studied, i.e., competence, access and embrace. The respective outcomes provide an overview of the ‘behavioural change’ anticipated to be achieved for the participants in the initiatives on a more general level.

4.1.1 Competence, access and embrace

While the combined results are impressive and indicate a clear increase in competence, there are considerable differences between the initiatives (table 5)¹⁰. In the two **bike school** initiatives that targeted competence specifically (case 12, Sweden and case 1, Belgium), the eight participants interviewed all increased competence, going from not being able to cycle to being able to cycle in a park or in traffic. The Swedish bike schools, case 10 and 11, targeted a combination of competence and access, providing tricycles for seniors and disabled people to use during practice time. Most of the eleven participants interviewed went from not being able to cycle to being able to cycle within the initiative. A few also indicated being able to cycle in a park or in traffic.

Table 5: Competence before and after taking part in the initiative

Competence	Participants		Facilitators' estimate	
	Before	After	Before	After
Not able to cycle	51.1% (24)	0.0% (0)	43.3% (13)	0.0% (0)
Able to cycle within initiative	0.0% (0)	21.4% (10)	23.3% (7)	20.0% (6)
Able to cycle in park	27.7% (13)	21.3% (10)	13.3% (4)	23.3% (7)
Able to cycle in traffic	21.3% (10)	57.4% (27)	20.0% (6)	56.7% (17)
Total	100.0% (47)	100.0% (47)	100.0% (30)	100.0% (30)

In one **bike-to-school** initiative (case 4, Italy), four parents were asked to assess their children's competence and they all indicated they had gone from not being able to cycle to being able to cycle within the initiative. To participate in bike-to-school actions everyone had to be able to ride a bike. In the second Italian case, a bike kitchen, the initiative targeted competence (e.g., bike maintenance) not captured by this scale and all four participants already knew how to cycle. The Romanian initiatives involved the installation of bike racks (case 8) and campaign aimed at promoting cycling (case 9). While not targeting competence directly, half of the eight individuals interviewed had started cycling independently in traffic because of the initiative. The Greek initiative included, amongst other things, a bike school and regular collective bike rides. Most of the ten participants knew how to cycle

¹⁰ Facilitators' estimates indicate their general assessment, not their assessment of the specific participants taking part in the study.

before the initiative but lacked the confidence to cycle in traffic. After taking part, all could cycle independently in traffic.

The facilitators were asked to assess the competence of the typical participants, too. The answers largely agree with the participants' assessment. The interviews with the facilitators also add insight into cases where interviews with participants proved difficult to conduct, primarily because the target groups were children. In one bike-to-school initiative (case 2, Belgium) the five facilitators interviewed indicated quite modest impact on competence as most children already knew how to cycle. In Portugal, cases 6 and 7 aim to promote cycling inclusion in disadvantaged areas, with youth as the primary target group. They include bike kitchens as well as other activities. In addition to six interviews with facilitators, three group interviews with young people aged between 10 and 16 were conducted. The overall result from these cases was that the children had some cycling competence, but limited awareness of how to cycle safely. The main outcome was being able to cycle independently in a park.

Better story: Developing competences

De Fietsschool ("The Cycling School") has existed since the beginning of 2012 and was started in Leuven by Mobiel21, with the support of the city authorities, the KU Leuven (university), and local neighbourhood associations. It was started because there was a need for a structured programme of cycling lessons for (migrant) women; before, there were only sporadic lessons for migrant women which focused more on the integration aspect. Initially, the programme worked with twelve lessons across four modules, representing different stages in the learning process (i.e., how to cycle, traffic rules, how to navigate in traffic, how to maintain a bike).

However, they noticed that there were a lot of people who completed the first module and did not join the subsequent modules, and that there were a lot of people who repeated the first module multiple times. These reflections lead to the current iteration of the initiative (launched three years later), consisting of one comprehensive course of 15 lessons (people who register are meant to complete 15 lessons, instead of just one module). Lessons are organised twice per week, spread over about 8 weeks, and it allows for more flexibility: i.e., people who learn the basics faster can go into traffic faster and those who need more time are also accommodated. While this initiative focused on Leuven, the initiative is also organised in a host of other municipalities across Flanders.

Regarding outcomes, it is difficult to draw general conclusions as some people drop out and others take a bit longer to get to a high enough level. The people who stick with the 15-lesson plan can generally cycle at the end, but not always in traffic (yet). Real examples of successful stories are people who start using electric bikes, commute to work by bike, or even use cargo bikes to transport their kids.

The initiative has existed for more than ten years already and has, in that time, grown a lot, both in terms of geography and expertise/knowhow. It is a very popular initiative and the (unfortunately) limited number of spaces get filled in quickly. The initiative also seems well-known in the city where it started (Leuven), which is a big advantage. They mostly focus on aspects of competence, which influences 'embrace', but they have not forgotten about the 'access' aspect either, providing bicycles for a limited time after the end of the lessons. This kind of holistic approach is important to guarantee the longer-term success of an initiative like this. The fact that Belgium is a cycling country also helps a lot, since car drivers in urban areas are presumably relatively aware and considerate of cyclists on the road compared to other countries.

As can be seen in Table 6, several initiatives also impacted access. Yet, the overall effect is not as strong as the impact on competence. In the Belgian (case 1) and Swedish (case 12) bike schools for immigrant women, most of the participants still had no access to a bike after the initiative took place. However, it was common that participants planned to buy a bike after having taken part in the initiative – should they afford one. Case 10 and 11 are bike schools for seniors and disabled to learn and practice using trike bikes. Most seniors in Case 10 had cycled all their life, but for various reasons were no longer able to use a regular bike. They may have been in accidents, or faced balance problems, and could no longer use regular bikes. The initiatives provided access to expensive trike bikes, but very few of the participants had access to trikes outside the initiative. In the two Italian cases, as well as the Greek case, all but one participant had access to a suitable bike prior to the initiative, hence the impact was limited.

Table 6: Access before and after taking part in the initiative

Access	Participants		Facilitators' estimate	
	Before	After	Before	After
No access to bike	34.0% (16)	17.0% (8)	53.3% (16)	16.7% (5)
Bike unfit to needs	14.9% (7)	8.5% (4)	13.3% (4)	20.0% (6)
Bike fit to needs	51.1% (24)	74.5% (35)	33.3% (10)	63.3% (19)
Total	100.0% (47)	100.0% (47)	100.0% (30)	100.0% (30)

The same applies to the Belgian bike-to-school initiative where facilitators estimated most children had prior access to bikes. The Romanian cases appear to have had an indirect effect on access, and four out of eight participants indicate an improvement. For example, one young woman decided to bring her bike from her hometown when safe storage was introduced. Operating in areas where the cost of a bicycle constitutes a major hindrance, the Portuguese cases have perhaps the greatest potential impact on access. Through lending bikes and offering opportunities to mend broken ones, they appear to have made an impact and interviews with participants and facilitators both indicate that access has improved, although the bikes did not always suit the participants' needs.

Better story: bikes as means for social inclusion in Lisbon bike kitchen

The cycling promotion in the CICLOPES initiative aims to achieve several broader goals. The primary objectives extend beyond merely encouraging cycling; they focus on social inclusion, empowerment, education and sustainable mobility.

The facilitator *Cláudia* outlines the following key goals for Bike kitchen Ciclopes:

Social Inclusion and Empowerment: To use bicycles to help participants gain autonomy, “even if it’s just to go out and explore.”

Skill Development and Education: To equip youth with practical skills and foster critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. “Teaching young people how to repair and maintain their bicycles not only equips them with practical skills but also promotes problem-solving and critical thinking.”

Creating Positive Perceptions and Self-Esteem: To change the perception of bicycles and enhance the self-esteem of youth. “The project has two main objectives: the first is to create a cool image for

bicycles, and the second is to increase access to bicycles by reducing economic, operational and technical barriers.”

Community Building and Engagement: To build stronger community ties and engage youth in positive activities. “Community events and pop-up activities in various neighbourhoods encourage participation and make cycling a fun and attractive option.”

Sustainable Mobility and Environmental Awareness: To promote environmentally friendly transportation and raise awareness about sustainability. “I believe in the power of bicycles to bring about social change and provide a sustainable mode of transport.”

We define ‘embrace’ as being about making the cycling system ‘yours’, mastering cycling, feeling positive about it, knowing that cycling fits with your identity and image and having reasons to ride and destinations to ride to (van der Kloof, 2022). As table 7 shows, embracing cycling was a common outcome of taking part in the initiatives, but here too we find differences between cases. Since ‘embrace’ is quite open to subjective interpretation, some caution is perhaps warranted when making comparisons. Participants across the initiatives typically increased ‘embrace’ by one ‘step’ on the ladder (weak to medium, or medium to strong), but some also made bigger leaps. In the Greek case, for example, eight out of ten participants went from weak to strong embrace. In one case, case 10 focusing on seniors in Sweden, all participants already embraced cycling strongly before the initiative and the change was more down to embracing a different form of cycling.

Table 7: Embrace before and after taking part in the initiative

Embrace	Participants		Facilitators’ estimate	
	Before	After	Before	After
Weak	63.8% (30)	2.1% (1)	60.0% (18)	0.0% (0)
Medium	14.9% (7)	31.9% (15)	40.0% (12)	66.7% (20)
Strong	21.3% (10)	66.0% (31)	0.0% (0)	33.3% (10)
Total	100% (47)	100% (47)	100.0% (30)	100.0% (30)

4.1.2 Behavioural outcomes

Competence, access and embrace are all important prerequisites for becoming a cyclist. Yet, a crucial question is whether participants did indeed cycle more after taking part in the initiatives. Two questions in the interview report addressed behavioural change: ‘Did participating in the initiative make the participant intend to change to more cycling outside the initiative?’ and ‘After the initiative, does the informant go cycling on a regular basis?’. The answers are summarised in tables 8 and 9.

Table 8: Responses to the question ‘Intent to change?’

Intent to change	
NA	12.8% (6)
No	12.8% (6)
Yes	74.5% (35)
Total	100,0% (47)

Table 9: Responses to the question ‘Cycle regularly after initiative?’

Cycle regularly	
NA	23.4% (11)
No	17.0% (8)
Yes	59.6% (28)
Total	100.0% (47)

Most participants intend to cycle more after taking part in one of the initiatives (table 8). ‘Yes’ was the most common answer across initiatives, with case 5, Italy (the bike kitchen) as the only exception where ‘NA’ was the main answer given. In this and other cases, ‘not applicable’ (NA) was typically chosen for participants who already cycled frequently prior to taking part in an initiative. ‘No’ overlaps somewhat with NA and was also used for some participants who were already committed cyclists, but for a few participants, cycling more outside of the initiative was never the main aim. Several participants in case 11 in Sweden, focusing on paracycling, used the training sessions mainly as an exercise opportunity. To another participant of the same initiative, the barriers to cycle outside of the initiative were still too high for it to be an option.

The results shown in table 9 follow a similar pattern but with slightly fewer ‘yes’ answers. As in table 8, NA can refer to participants who already cycled regularly (both Italian cases are in this category). For some of the participants in the bike schools, ‘no’ (Belgium, case 1) and ‘NA’ (Sweden, case 12) refers to individuals still in training, i.e., where it is too soon to tell. In case 11, Sweden, none of the participants cycle more outside the initiative, indicating either a lack of competence, lack of access to suitable bikes or limited interest.

4.1.3 Other outcomes

Cycling initiatives had impacts beyond mere transport. Many participants reported that they felt empowered, gained independence and a sense of freedom, and had improved their health by cycling. The Greek case showed some impressive results in this regard, including participants feeling supported to adopt more affordable means of transport in their everyday life.

The importance of the *cycling* component varies between the studied initiatives. For some initiatives, cycling as well as the ambition to lower barriers to cycling for disadvantaged groups are a tool for achieving broader social goals. In general, the results show that the initiatives did not only have an impact on improving general mobility but also on reaching other goals, such as increased employability, breaking social isolation, increased well-being, improved child-parent relations, integration, language skills, political awareness and activism, inclusive safe space for “being oneself” – including LGBTQ+ (bike kitchen, Rome).

All teams found some form of outcome in this regard. The Fietsschool (case 1) supports **social interaction** among people of different backgrounds, which was anticipated to lead to lasting and positive relationships. The local volunteers of the school got to know people who are often new to the city/neighbourhood and enjoyed that they can help with their integration through cycling. School op de Teller (case 2) reported outcomes regarding how the involved pupils **attained more insight into the traffic conditions** of their neighbourhoods and school areas. In theory, it also shows them that they can have a voice in co-creation and public debates around mobility, although the practical results of the researched iterations of this initiative leave room for improvement in this regard.

Other outcomes concern the **formation of community**, and such communities provide room for **capacity-building for cycling** – especially for people who took up cycling in contexts where cycling was less common. The Italian bike kitchen (case 5) noted how the bike kitchen made people feel empowered to find a like-minded group that helps them validate their choices, making them feel included and giving them the moral support to “*resist the mainstream system and keep pedalling!*” (IT09). An impact of community was also telling for the Italian bike-to-school case (4). They reported that people participating in Bike-to-school emphasised how this makes them feel part of a cycling community.

The initiatives that supported cycling with trike bikes among seniors and disabled people (case 10 and 11) also made efforts to **support social aspects and break social isolation** for their participants. For some participants, especially seniors, the social aspects were more important than the cycling practice, pointing to how initiatives like these, if available, can form an important social arena. The initiatives provide a social platform to which participants can come over time and practice cycling when it suits them. They are part of the cycling community, and this is also reflected in the informal talks where participants get to know each other and form new friendships.

Inequalities related to socioeconomic barriers, i.e. access, can be reduced by the initiatives, even though costs remain a significant barrier for the most vulnerable groups. **Structural barriers** in how transport systems neglect the needs of disabled, older persons and children was in general reduced to a lesser extent by the initiatives. These groups still face barriers outside the initiative due to their own or their parents' perceptions of real or imagined risks.

Gender roles, ideals and meanings related to gender and cycling in immigrant women's 'home' countries was in general challenged by the initiatives. Gendered and cultural barriers could be overcome in countries with stronger cycling cultures, where cycling was 'normal' and more widely available. Primarily women with immigrant backgrounds challenged gender roles in their new country. The women also had very clear reasons to why they needed to learn to bike, where factors such as employability, being able to cycle with their kids, health, reduced costs and commitment to cycling enabled change. But they also expressed concerns about feeling unsafe when cycling in mixed traffic as beginners.

4.2 Factors explaining outcomes per cluster of initiatives

This section takes a closer look at the factors that can explain the varying and different outcomes in the four clusters of initiatives studied. The factors will be discussed in relation to *outreach* activities and *diversity* within the initiative, and *how* they facilitate change and for *whom*, taking into account gender+ intersectionality.

4.2.1 Bike schools: Developing cycling competence

Bike schools facilitate change by providing suitable bikes, instructions how to use them and a safe space to practice. In short, they develop cycling competence. There are four bike schools in the sample (cases 1, 10, 11, 12), two in Belgium and two in Sweden. Their target groups are different, focusing on seniors, disabled people and women with immigrant background. This allows us to compare impacts regarding intersections of age, gender and disability vis-a-vis how the participants perceive their ability to change and take up cycling in their everyday life.

Outreach activities

The Swedish trike bike school for seniors manages to reach their target group, but in declining numbers and most are women with Swedish background. The initiative engages with other organisations for seniors, but not with organisations that may **organise people with more diverse ethnic backgrounds**. Lack of time and resources were the main barrier for increased outreach activities.

The trike bike school for disabled also manages to reach their target group but has problems recruiting new participants to the organisation. The age span is wider for this group, some 'older' 60+ and some 'younger' who are in their thirties. Even though the facilitators presented ideas how to reach more and younger potential participants (e.g., recruit in schools, show young people in wheelchair that tricycles

are available), the organisers found **lack of time** and **problems accessing schools** as barriers for recruitment.

The bike schools for women (cases 1 and 12) also manage to reach their target groups. Both initiatives (BE and SE) are well connected to their municipality and have strategic ties to institutions that work with the target group that can point them in their direction (i.e., language schools, churches or other meeting places of importance). Factors contributing to the relatively successful outreach activities among the bike schools targeting women is the fact that they are established and well-known organisations in the neighbourhoods where they operate. Their longevity contributes to building trust and accessibility for the communities living there and lowers thresholds for participation.

In sum, identified factors for successful outreach are the combination of **time**, developed **strategies**, and **networks** for communication with target groups and initiative.

Role of diversity among volunteers

Previous studies have noted that diversity among staff can have an impact on the outreach to and participation of under-represented groups (van der Kloof, 2022). The bike schools studied do not show great diversity among staff. All instructors for case 1 and 12 were women, often middle aged from the majority population. One initiative (case 12) had tried to recruit instructors from the participant group but failed. The situation is somewhat different for the trike bike schools (case 10, 11), which had facilitators of different ages, genders and disabilities. Their facilitators said they considered diversity in staff important, mainly for normalising the presence of disabled people in the role as instructors. However, the division of labour followed gendered patterns, with (disabled) men facilitated training and bikes and women facilitated coffee and snacks. None of the interviewed bike school participants mentioned they perceived a 'lack of diversity' as a hindering factor for their participation or for developing their cycling competence – they generally felt welcome and well taken care of.

A dominant narrative across the interviews with bike schools is that it is in general **difficult to recruit volunteers**. This in turn makes it difficult to plan and scale up the initiatives. Since volunteers found satisfaction in seeing their volunteer work pay off in cycling uptake, lack of participation could have negative impact on volunteers' willingness to invest time and effort in the initiatives.

In sum, the satisfaction of participants was in general not affected by lack of diversity among volunteers. Rather, the **reciprocal relation between facilitators and participants** comes up as an important factor for supporting change.

Factors supporting change

The bike schools developed cycling competence for their participants by offering support to overcome balance problems and fear of falling, they did this both hands-on and/or verbally. The bike schools have developed intuitive ways of **overcoming potential language barriers**, like explaining traffic signs in a way that is not technical but emphasises the essentials. Instructions could be given in either Swedish or Dutch, as part of a language training. Body language and language that centres on the bike and its parts are common. Any 'cultural' hinderances (clothes, hair, bodily issues) are handled with sensitivity for supporting their cycling practice (case 12). A challenge is to facilitate saddles for women suffering from genital mutilation and who face great difficulties using standard bike saddles. Various support was offered to provide more comfortable saddles – gel supported saddles and saddles in different shapes – which succeeded in some cases but not for all (case 12).

The bike schools had **different approaches to support cycling competence**. The trike bike schools offered individual support to increase technical skills based on the participants' individual capacities, but not with the goal of cycling in traffic. By contrast, the bike schools for immigrant women supported

progressions following a specific ‘step by step’ schedule to support their learning to be able to cycle in traffic (case 1 and 12). The Belgian bike school have an advanced 15-step programme that they follow to develop the participants’ cycling competence fully. However, they also experienced large dropouts from their courses since not all women succeeded in following the entire course. By contrast, the Swedish bike school had developed a much simpler step-by-step programme to support participants’ progression – with the last step being cycling in traffic to practice traffic rules. Here the main strategy was to keep a low threshold for participation. Participants simply had to show up, they did not have to sign up in advance, which made participation easier for women with care responsibilities. This arrangement was perceived of as ‘what works’ for the target group to be able to participate, but required the organisers to be flexible – having to sometimes take care for very large groups of participants and in other times only a few. Regarding outcomes, it is difficult to draw general conclusions as some people drop out and others take a bit longer to get to a high enough level. In the Belgian case, the people who stick with the 15-lesson plan can generally cycle at the end, but not always in traffic (yet). The same goes for the Swedish case where most participants said they learned to cycle, but not necessarily in in traffic.

Compared with the trike bike school outcomes, the impact was much more significant for the participants in the bike schools for women (as also noted in 4.1). In the two bike school initiatives for *women with immigrant backgrounds* (case 1 and 12), the eight participants interviewed all increased their competence, going from not being able to cycle to being able to cycle in a park or in traffic. By contrast, the bike schools targeting *seniors and disabled people* (case 10 and 11) showed different outcomes. Most of the eleven participants interviewed went from not being able to cycle to being able to cycle within the initiative, but not in a park or in traffic.

There are some obvious reasons for these differences, primarily related to **age and ability**. The women in case 1 and 12 were in general younger and able bodied compared to the sometimes much older/or disabled trike bike school participants. The bike schools for women mainly helped them to overcome doubts and anxieties about their own abilities to cycle (i.e., afraid of falling), though more experience to cycle in traffic seemed necessary for some participants to fully overcome these concerns. As able bodied and relatively young, the participants were able to improve their cycling abilities after participation in the initiative, with the interviewees becoming more confident to cycle in a controlled environment (i.e., with an instructor present) and in most cases they were well on the way to cycle independently on the road.

Cycling culture had a positive impact on cycling participation. The fact that “everyone cycles” supported change in both the Swedish and Belgian cases. When moving to Sweden, Sabine realised how common it was to cycle, also for women, which pushed her to join the cycling school (SE01). She also needed to be able to cycle to increase her chances to get a job. For Iman, (BE06) living in Leuven, most of her female friends knew how to cycle – “I felt sorry that I could not go along”. With cycling being ‘common’, you simply had to learn for social reasons. Elly says: “when its summertime everyone has a bike and cycle around, [...] then you feel like why not give it a try and learn?”

Children’s cycling abilities was a contributing factor for mothers learning to cycle. Amy, a 28-year-old Nigerian student currently living in Sweden, grew up in an environment where cycling was “only for the poor” (SE08). For her, learning to bike was a way to accompany her daughter to daycare, “she can ride a bike as 6 years old, I must learn”. Similar examples exist in the Belgian case study. Samira, a 50-year-old woman with an 8-year-old daughter, is from a country where women are ‘not supposed to cycle’: “I was afraid, did not learn how to ride a bike as a child or adult, even though the idea was attractive” (BE05). Now she learns how to ride a bike to accompany (and protect) her daughter (“She already bikes, so I cannot wait too long”).

For disabled persons, factors that would support change are **access to special bikes** and **assistance** outside of the bike school. 63-year-old Karin sits in a wheelchair and cycles with the help of her hands on a hand-pedalled bicycle. She occasionally borrows a “side by side” electric bike from the municipality to use during the summer month. With this special bike, she can ride with her feet and get out more, but she needs an assistant to ‘see’ and guide for her. During the summer month, when there are no scheduled activities in the bike school, Sofia says she can borrow a trike bike to use privately. This way she may continue to exercise by bike. Sofia says, “I would like to cycle more in everyday life, my biggest obstacle for this is the cost, I cannot afford to buy a bike that costs 4,000 Euro just like that, so it is the financial part that is the biggest obstacle” (SE15).

Another factor supporting change is **concerns about the environment**. Mary, a 29-year-old student from Bangladesh currently living in Sweden, is one of very few participants who connects cycling with experiences of climate change, which in turn is a strong reason why she wants to re-learn how to cycle. For her, cycling is a way to “*do something*” for the environment and show respect for those who live with climate change, such as her mother.

Summary

An important factor for developing cycling competence across all bike schools studied was that the schools provided **safe spaces** and **hands-on support** where participants could feel comfortable to practice without embarrassment. The bike school for women had the most significant impact on supporting its participants to take up cycling in their everyday life. Most of the participants expressed a strong embrace and commitment to cycling after having taken part in the initiative. A contributing factor for this impact was that many of the participating women had very strong reasons to why they wanted to learn to cycle: **for their employability, for social reasons, for being able to cycle with their kids, to reduce transport costs, for health reasons or for the environment**. They also had the **bodily capacities** for cycling in traffic which was not the case for the disabled and old(er) aged cyclist. While the disabled and the seniors emphasised **health and breaking social isolations** as reasons for participating in the initiatives, they often hesitated to cycle outside the initiative entirely, due to lack of self-efficacy and feeling unsafe in traffic or because of being depending on assistance.

4.2.2 Bike-to-schools: Developing cycling competence for children

Bike-to-school initiatives facilitate change by supporting competence and embrace. They teach children how to cycle to school and around the city (competence) and thereby facilitate a context where they can experience city cycling and “feel like” cyclists (embrace). The two bike-to-school initiatives studied are quite different in their approaches:

- In the Italian bike-to-school initiative based in Rome (case 4) children and parents participate with their own bicycles. It is an initiative that starts when parents want to take their children on a bike and want them to cycle. Participants are in 3rd, 4th and 5th grades and ends when the children no longer go to that school and the parents no longer have any interest in proposing it to children other than their own children.
- The Belgian *School op de Teller* (case 2) also targets children, The participants of this initiative are pupils in the 4th, 5th and 6th grades (~10-12 years old). This initiative is more than a bike-to-school initiative, potentially influencing a whole community to adopt more safe and sustainable modes of transport. Instead of supporting competence in cycling to school, the *School op de Teller* facilitates change toward more and more inclusive cycling through motivating children to bike-to-school, as well as addressing hindrances and obstacles (addressing unsafety, as well as perceived unsafety by parents). Kids that lack motoric skills and traffic insight are supported further in gym class.

Outreach activities and role of diversity among volunteers

The two bike-to-school initiatives studied (case 2 and 4) target different groups and do different things. The Italian initiative (4) target participants from the entire school. The school is very multicultural, and half of the families have immigrant backgrounds, but the participating groups tend to be Italian. Despite their all-welcome approach and use of multi-language communication, inclusion challenges remain. As the organizer Benedetta says: “Of course for parents with a migration background it is always a bit of a conundrum to see if they can understand what we are communicating, and therefore if they do not participate because they did not understand or if they do not consider participation important”. Parents are usually already very sensitised to the topic and may already be parents who cycle “to school or use bicycles”. (Benedetta, 50 years old, IT03). The average participant is a parent and a child from an Italian or at most a mixed family. Since parents need to take part in the initiative – which requires time – it is mainly those parents who have flexible work arrangements who can participate. In practice, the typical participant knows how to cycle, lives in the area and has non-immigrant background. **Time and parental involvement can be both a supporting and limiting factor** for this initiative. For those families who do have the time and capacity to participate, taking part in the initiative contributes to strengthen feelings of support as part of a wider community of cyclists.

By contrast, the Belgian initiative focuses on students in specific school classes – with the aim to get pupils involved in cycling and their broader environments/mobility needs. Whether they participate or not depends on whether the school they are enrolled in has adopted the initiative or not. If a school participates, the “School op de Teller” lessons are included in their curriculum. While the initiative’s primary focus is on elementary school-aged children they do not prioritise any specific vulnerabilities other than young age. In practice, the often-rural setting of the schools adds an extra potential vulnerability dimension, but the lack of focus on other inequalities makes it so that this initiative usually does not reach marginalised groups beyond those represented in a specific school class (or only coincidentally).

Even though both initiatives target school children and seek to influence pupils and their parents to take up more sustainable transport habits, their way of working is different, as is their conditions to reach diversity within the initiative.

Factors supporting change

The factors affecting the outcomes for the two compared initiatives is different, with the role of the **parents** at centre stage. For the Italian bike-to-school case, where the parents are already convinced cyclists, they facilitated the initiative and was key drivers to support change. For the already convinced participants, embrace was primarily strengthened for these participating families – 3 out of 4 of the interviewed parents already cycled daily. According to their parents, the children wanted to bike on a more regular basis after the initiative, not just as a hobby. Challenges remained to find ways to support cycling and inclusion for more marginalised families in the area.

For the Belgian School op de Teller, most of the pupils indicated that in general, the initiative did not lead them to cycle more often. However, the initiative did have an impact on some pupils to potentially cycling more, like preparing them for riding a bike to high school or cycling despite bad weather. The initiative is relatively new, which makes it difficult to appreciate any long-term consequences already, but the fact that its main beneficiaries – the children – are **involved in co-creating solutions** to the mobility issues that characterise their area will likely give them a sense of ownership. Children’s direct involvement is a factor that can have positive effects regarding how they perceive themselves as

cyclists and potentially strengthen their sense of capacity to influence the shaping of their living environments, particularly in terms of opportunities for cycling and safety.

Support from schools and teachers comes up as a **factor for strengthening children's involvement** in cycling issues. The Italian bike-to-school initiative was supported by the school for endorsing and promoting the initiative. The Belgian school op de Teller initiative required that the teachers are motivated as they are usually the ones who applied for the project and who contribute to an encouraging atmosphere. Ideally, parents are also involved from the beginning so that they can be supportive of their children within the framework of this initiative. However, teachers (especially from the rural site in the School of de Teller) were worried over the increased lack of traffic insight and even motoric skills among some pupils, suspecting the parents to be increasingly or even excessively 'overprotective'.

Summary

While support from schools and teachers are enabling factors for developing cycling competence for children, both initiatives put focus on parents as hindering and enabling factors for children's capacity to cycle. As in the Italian case, the **parents' dedication** to cycling and their engagement in the initiative was a **strong enabling factor** for supporting children's cycling in a highly car dominated city such as Rome. By contrast, in the Belgian case, the parents were rather considered to be **inhibiting change** as they tended to prevent their children from cycling to school (on their own) because of concerns about road safety. **Potentially**, if issues with inclusion and parents' concerns about risks can be overcome, bike-to-school initiatives can help change the mobility habits of a family, motivating them to take the bicycle to school more often and/or using the bicycle for other kinds of trips. In addition, the school and wider neighbourhoods may benefit from such initiatives since they get to engage with the perspective of the children on mobility issues and can make use of the suggestions for change that pupils, teachers and parents have come up with.

4.2.3 Bike kitchens: Providing competence and access to bikes

In general, bike kitchens emphasise the importance of embodied practical knowledge and are empowering people to gain independence through competence in how to fix bikes. Bike kitchens facilitate change by sharing ideas, problems and solutions through (embodied) bike knowledge. In the sample, we have in total three initiatives that can be categorized as bike kitchens. They represent some important differences among them in terms of target groups, outreach activities and potential impacts.

Outreach activities and role of diversity among volunteers

The bike kitchen Ciclofficina in Rome is run by a group of cycling activists who also co-organise bicycle protests and events aligned with anti-racist, anti-fascist, anti-sexist ideologies. The Ciclofficina was built within a network of Roman bike kitchens and activist movements. The movement was born together with the Critical Mass as a political movement. The main idea of both the bike kitchen and the Critical Mass is to put into practice the political aspects that come out of antagonistic circles against petrol addiction, spending money on cars, queuing in traffic, etc. The volunteer Greg (IT05) says that they reach out to all cyclists: "We are here to welcome cyclists and show them that the bicycle is a versatile means of transport that can be maintained independently. If we can convince one person to switch to cycling, it means that there is one less person in a car on the road". As for the target group, he says that the cycle workshops are for all kinds of people: "We're trying to improve society with bicycles, and not only that, but we also want to be inclusive."

Volunteers promote access to bikes, competence in mending them, and produce a strong embrace through activism. But at the same time, the **strong sense of group and community belonging** that is formed in the bike kitchen may also exclude participants who do not subscribe to the activist approach. The people who visit the bike kitchen are often from the middle or upper-middle social classes who have the possibility to devote part of their time to the initiative. Despite these challenges, once part of the community, the bike kitchen seems willing to work with issues related to intersectionality and inclusion in the bike kitchen itself, committed to anti-sexist language and to prevent any issues with harassments etc in the workshop.

The Lisbon bike kitchens are cooperatives established to foster projects with both environmental and social impact. This is done in collaboration with a broad network of local organizations (case 6), and through religious organisations and the Lisbon city council among others (case 7). The Ciclopes initiative (case 6) also receives funding from the European Social Fund and national funding from the Portugal 2020 strategy. This makes the Portuguese bike kitchens more secure in terms of their organisational continuation, but also broader in terms of their potential outreach and impacts that reaches beyond mere cycling or cycling politics.

Their outreach activities are directed through associations or people who know the community. By organizing community events and pop-up activities, CICLOPES attracts attention and interest from local youth. These events are intended to provide a non-intimidating entry point for new participants. A typical participant is not only interested in learning bike mechanics but are attracted to the opportunity to gain mobility and explore areas beyond their immediate neighbourhood, providing a sense of freedom and independence. The programme employs a diverse team of staff and facilitators from various backgrounds, including bicycle mechanics, social workers, educators and community members. This team is responsible for the day-to-day operations, including running workshops, organizing events and engaging with participants.

The initiative manages to reach their target groups. Participants vary in age and ethnicity, from younger children to older teens, both natives, immigrants and ethnic minorities. However, despite ambitions and success to be inclusive, challenges with gender representation remains. Gender representation in staff is an important factor for gender inclusion. When female facilitators are present, more girls participate, but when the leadership is male-dominated, fewer girls join in. The facilitator Cláudia notes that: “In Bairro de Padre Cruz, when we had [female name] there, I saw a lot more girls. I wouldn’t say they were the majority, but there were more. For the moment I have three guys there, when I look down, 90% of the time it’s guys” (PT02).

Factors supporting change

The facilitator of the Italian activist bike kitchen says that they had an impact on participants’ way of moving, namely that people “have changed their way of moving, embracing the bicycle completely thanks to the initiative.” (IT04) According to Riccardo, the bike kitchen is a stepping stone for abandoning old habits and learning new ones. However, all the participants interviewed for the Roman bike kitchen were people already particularly engaged in cycling whose ‘embrace’ got strengthened through participating in the bike kitchen activities and becoming part of its community. Only in one case (IT07) was participation in the cycle workshop decisive in changing behaviour and embracing cycling as the main means of transport. The interviewees from the Rome bike kitchen emphasized feeling marginalized primarily as *cyclists* in a car dominated city, and that the bike kitchen **provided a strong sense of community** – a factor that supported their identities as cyclists and strengthened their capacity to continue cycling. Regarding **competence**, participants say they learn a lot about how to do small repairs to the bicycle, which likely makes them more autonomous in handling the maintenance of their bicycle.

The importance of community that came up so strongly in the Rome bike kitchen can be contrasted with the social bike kitchens studied in Lisbon. Here, there was a noticeable gender disparity in participation. Boys tended to frequent the kitchen more and use bikes to much greater extent than girls. **Ciclopes bike kitchen** especially supported those who cannot afford to buy a bike, such as disadvantaged youth, migrants, and refugees who are – in practice – more often young boys.

The initiative supported change by enhancing participants access to bicycles, supporting their skills in riding and maintaining bikes, and encouraged a positive attitude towards cycling activities. Some participants also learned to ride and repair bicycles through the Ciclopes initiative, while others already had some cycling experience. All nine participants in the group interview reported that at the time of the interview, they could ride a bike, although they acknowledged a significant lack of knowledge about traffic safety. However, the initiative's impact on their embrace remains modest. While the interviewees indicated that participating in the initiative has encouraged most of them to cycle more regularly and consider incorporating cycling into their routines beyond the organised activities, there was still a clear preference for cars and motorbikes as their primary means of future transportation.

Summary

The bike kitchens facilitated change by enhancing participants **access to bicycles, supporting their skills** in riding and maintaining bikes, and encouraged a **positive attitude** towards cycling activities. However, the studied bike kitchens represent contrasting cases in terms of goals, outreach and the role of bikes in facilitating change. While the Roman bike kitchen was more leaning towards an 'anti car' activist movement oriented to improving the transport system for cyclists, the Lisbon bike kitchens primarily use bikes to target social inequalities in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. The Roman bike kitchen managed to produce a strong **sense of community** formed around cyclists' sense of 'unbelonging' in the car centred transport system and their ambition to strengthening the cycling culture in Rome. By contrast, despite generally positive experiences and enjoyment of cycling, most of the Lisbon bike kitchen participants still favoured motorised vehicles. This is also in line with more general travel patterns in Lisbon indicating a **weak cycling culture** with only 1.34 percent of Lisbon's resident population using bicycles as their primary mode of transportation for work or study (Census 2021). Even though the initiative successfully reached marginalised groups and **managed to lower barriers related to access and competence**, the results indicate participants' relatively weak embrace of cycling.

4.2.4 Bike promotion: Building cycling communities

Initiatives clustered under the headline *bike promotion* support cycling uptake in a more general way compared to the specialised initiatives discussed above. The studied initiatives support cycling mainly for able-bodied adults and students, which includes marginalised and vulnerable groups. Moreover, they do so in contexts where cycling is neglected and lacking suitable infrastructure. The bike promotion initiatives studied are non-profit organisations in wider alliances seeking to provide platforms for bike promotion.

Outreach activities and role of diversity among volunteers

The Greek case (3) supports change by organising events for the promotion of cycling and the principle of sustainable mobility within urban Thessaloniki. The events organised by the Cycling Sports Association of Thessaloniki (CAT) are sporadic, and some planned during the study period could not take place due to low participation. The initiative was open to anyone wanting to join and managed to attract people with various vulnerabilities, including socioeconomic and psychological

difficulties, while others joined to learn cycling in the city with more confidence, mostly women but also some old(er) men. Through their actions in second-chance schools and in disadvantaged neighbourhoods in the western part of Thessaloniki, the initiative reaches out to marginalised individuals, especially women. They advertise their activities on Facebook and other online platforms. The core members and **organisers are women**, this in turn was described as a significant factor for attracting other women to feel comfortable and inspired to take part. The women representation among organisers enables them to recruit women participants who otherwise would not have taken part. Kiki (EL01), one of the participants, notes that: “CAT is run mostly by (female name), something that makes us [women] feel more welcome, I think. It automatically makes it look like it is possible for us to participate actively in cycling activities”. The main outreach barrier is **time and funding**, the facilitators work on voluntary basis which limits their capacity.

The Romanian bike initiatives *The Green zones for bikes* and *Bike2school* (case 8 and 9) support cycling as a form of sustainable mobility in the city Iasi – a city with close to 300 000 inhabitants with very poor cycling infrastructure. The initiatives support change by providing access to safe places to keep the bike while in school, and by promoting cycling as a sustainable, affordable and pleasant way of mobility around the town. As other studies have pointed to, the risk of theft is a “nagging worry” for cyclists, and that knowing there is safe parking available can have a positive impact on cycling uptake (Edberg, 2023, 9). The Bike2school promotes cycling through social media platforms, press releases, lobbying, and by participating in actions and activities that encourage young people to cycle (such as installing bikes racks in schools). The initiatives support participants to become more self-efficient, especially young female students. The bike-to-school initiative was open for cyclists at the university and was promoted through social media. They managed to reach both vulnerable and marginalized groups with socioeconomic difficulties, especially among students, employees and members of the community in the initiative.

Factors supporting change

After having taken part in Cycling Sports Association of Thessaloniki (CAT) actions, all participants said they intended to change their mobility habits to more cycling. From mainly using the bike around their neighbourhood and mainly for leisure, they started cycling daily to commute to the city centre for work or to do everyday activities. Eight out of ten participants moved from weak to strong embrace, one from weak to medium embrace and one already had a strong embrace. Participants were **motivated** to start cycling because of either **health** reasons (depression, chronic stress disorder, diabetes, cancer survivor) and/or due to a **poor financial situation**. As an illustrative better story, we turn to Kiki, a 30-year-old unemployed woman who lives with her mother in a small apartment in the eastern part of Thessaloniki. After losing her job due to COVID she became unemployed and was later diagnosed with depression. To find ways to deal with her depression she started cycling but was very afraid at first. After finding out online about CAT she joined one of their regular bike activities and since then she started gradually using her bicycle in her everyday life. The initiative introduced cycling as a mode of transport available to her: “I just didn’t know it was possible. It was not in my ‘vocabulary’. I was raised in a neighbourhood where there were no cyclists. Almost everybody owned a car, and those who wouldn’t just took the bus. So, it is basically that I never thought about it.” (EL01)

Nowadays she is moving exclusively by bike, and she feels more positive about re-entering the workforce and society in general. The combination of participants’ motivation to cycle and that the initiative managed to create a women-inclusive learning environment are factors that contributed to participants overcoming their fear of cycling and gaining confidence in cycling (strong embrace). **Factors contributing to change** are that cycling is associated with **positive values** such as saving money, increased wellbeing (exercise and stress relief), and increased independence and confidence

in city cycling. The initiative contributed to forming **cycling communities** that could build the participants' capacity to take up cycling also in highly car-dense cities such as Thessaloniki. In addition, the organisation also engaged in **lobbying** for improved cycling infrastructure which was perceived as an important step for making cycling a legitimate form of transport in a city dominated by cars.

The impacts from Romanian *Green zone for bikes* and the *Bike2school* initiatives are more difficult to estimate. There are no general statistics on the number of users of the bike racks available, nor on their vulnerabilities or other intersections of importance. However, all the participants interviewed reported an increase in both access and level of embrace after the bike racks have been installed. Even though some of them were using bikes before the bike racks were made available, three out of four female student participants reported biking more frequently after the racks had been installed.

The availability of bike racks became a factor for **community building among cyclists**. The installation of the bike racks made available social activities based on cycling among the students. Iona notes: "I remembered that we took several pictures during the inauguration and put them on Instagram. The event felt special to us, gave us a reason to get together in the school yard." (RO02).

Iona was not cycling before she became a student but was convinced by her classmate to try cycling in the school yard. Afterwards, she took some cycling classes, and her parents bought her a bike and she now uses her bike regularly. Iona and Mara (RO01) both made **new friendships** among their classmates formed around cycling and are going biking in the city after classes. Both women moved from weak or medium embrace to strong embrace after participating in the initiative.

All four interviewed participants have had **support from family and friends to take up cycling**. They all stress the importance of **community** for enabling them to cycle in what is described as a very car-dense city with no dedicated lanes for cycling and drivers sometimes behaving "rude and aggressive" towards cyclists (Ana, RO03). The interviewed students talk about cycling as a **healthy alternative** and a **relief from the stress** associated with public transport. For Ana, who has a hearing disability, the bike racks made cycling to school available instead of, as previously, taking the bus. On her bike, she could escape the unwanted attention she normally got on public transport given her hearing disability and hearing device.

The second Romanian initiative *bike2school/bike2work* supports change through cycling promotion via online social media and through cycling supporting activities. The aim of the campaign was to encourage individuals to see cycling as a mode of transportation that could respond to their mobility needs and enhance physical and mental health. Most of the interviewed participants (4 out of 5) reported an increase in embrace and cycling competence after having participated in the campaign. Alin, a 22-year-old man living in Iasi, found out about the initiative from a co-worker who was cycling to work (RO02, case 2). Alin wanted **to find a more sustainable way of transportation** both for reducing transport costs and for improving his **physical health**. He is very satisfied with the initiative and emphasises the **social aspects of cycling** as it helped him to make friends and spend quality time with colleagues. As Alin stated: "when we go cycling, that's what defines us." Adina is a 21-year-old woman living in Iasi who suffers from social anxiety (RO03, case 2). Her therapist suggested doing outdoor activities within a group of people as part of her therapy. Through the initiative she started cycling to improve her health. Both Adina and Alin managed to move from weak to strong embrace thanks to the initiative.

Apart from providing **community** and a **sustainable alternative to cars**, the initiative managed to **develop participants' competence in how to find safe cycling routes**. For Elena (RO01, case2), a 28-year-old single mother living in Iasi, the facilitators helped her pick a safe route to start cycling

with her daughter to school. However, other interviewed parents with similarly aged children came to a different conclusion. Adrian is a 42-year-old married father with a child in a similar age as Elena. He learned about the initiative from a coworker who cycles to work daily but states that he could never cycle given his family responsibilities and lack of time (RO05, case 2). By contrast to Elena, who works from home and can cycle to school along a safe route, Adrian continues using his car for the obligations he must perform daily.

Summary

The bike promotion initiatives all provided potential cyclists with a sense of **safe spaces for developing their cycling competences** in car-dense cities. The initiatives managed to form **cycling communities** with impacts on the participants' cycling habits, social relations and cycling embrace. **Personal motivations** were contributing factors for change, such as a wish to find more sustainable transport and personal wellbeing. Other contributing factors for change was how cycling was associated with positive values such as saving money, increased wellbeing (exercise and stress relief), and increased independence. Unexpected outcomes were that material infrastructures such as bike racks could be a contributing factor in forming cycling communities. For Mara, Iona and Ana, the instalment of the bike racks initiated a wider process of change, including community building and establishment of new friendships. The **social support** from other students, family and friends enabled them to at least partially overcome barriers related to infrastructure and what they refer to as an aggressive car culture.

4.3 Summary factors, potentials and barriers for change

Individual level

Factors that contribute to behavioural change on an individual level are access to **safe spaces** and **hands-on support** for building cycling competence. This was especially important for women that faced various forms of barriers to cycling. Contributing factors for taking up cycling are personal motivations such as increased **employability, ability to cycle with children, reduced transport costs, health reasons, environmental and/or political reasons**.

In addition, the presence of a **strong cycling culture** supported individuals to take up cycling even if cycling has not been available to them previously. For seniors and disabled people, the situation was different. Even though initiatives managed to lower barriers for disabled and old(er) seniors to develop cycling competence, these groups rarely cycled on an everyday basis, due to lack of self-efficacy and due to feeling unsafe in traffic. Their main reasons for participation in the initiatives was primary for health reasons and for social reasons, as the cycling initiatives managed to break social isolation for these groups.

Cycling safety come forth as an overarching key barrier for change and for cycling inclusion across all initiatives – with different effects across intersections of gender, age, bodily ability, socioeconomic status and geographical location. While all cyclists are vulnerable in cities/places made for cars, some people are more **at odds** with the present transport systems across the sites, namely those who are both *vulnerable and dependent* on support (i.e. children, seniors, disabled).

The **support from a community** runs as a red thread through all initiatives as an important factor for supporting change. The initiatives all point to how important the sense of community was for facilitating change. Participants found support for change in their communities and developed strategies to fend for their safety (i.e. find safer routes, find ways of taking up space as cyclists, practice cycling in groups to build capacity).

While **support** from schools and teachers was an enabling factor for developing cycling competence for children, **the role of parents** was an important factor as they could be both supporters and barriers to (children's) cycling.

Initiative level

In most cases, the initiatives **managed to reach their intended target groups**, but with declining numbers of participants for some initiatives, struggling to find successful ways of recruiting. Some had problems recruiting as diverse as they wanted to – should they have **more time and resources to invest** in outreach. The main barrier for recruitment, including diverse recruitment, was lack of time, energy and volunteers. Successful outreach activities encompassed to establish trust with potential participants through direct contact, or via relevant organisations and platforms, to lower their threshold to participate.

The facilitation of women-inclusive learning environment was important to support cycling inclusion. The facilitation of **women-only spaces** for cycling practices was an important factor for reaching participants especially in the Swedish bike school for women. **Diversity in staff** was a factor for lowering barriers for underrepresented genders to participate in two of the initiatives especially. The bike promotion initiative in Thessaloniki (case 3) and the Lisbon bike kitchen (case 6) noted how the presence of women facilitators had significantly positive impacts on girls and women taking part in the activities.

Volunteers play an important role in facilitating change but were in general hard to recruit. While initiatives stressed that diversity in staff/volunteers was of importance, diversity was often hard to realise due to difficulties recruiting volunteers. It was unusual for the initiatives to recruit facilitators/instructors from their groups of participants.

Many of the initiatives are **bottom-up** initiatives that are very demanding for the volunteers to run, especially if there is a lot of bureaucracy involved. Maintaining a consistent volunteer base was a critical challenge that affected the initiatives' sustainability and reach. Limited resources and volunteer availability **can impact on the capacity of scaling up the project** to a larger audience or other areas.

4.4 “Better stories” and links to transformation

While all initiatives can be seen as 'better stories' with positive effects at an aggregate level, albeit in different ways and to varying degrees, some partners have also highlighted 'better stories' at an individual level. In Belgium, for example, Sandra (BE04) was on sick leave for her anxiety disorder. Then, she started attending De Fietsschool (case 1) because it was recommended by her therapist. She was not particularly interested in cycling, but she found the experience rewarding. She learnt how to cycle and became interested in continuing to cycle, because of her engagement with the initiative. In Greece, Jenny (EL10) was fighting depression after successfully battling breast cancer. She found participating in the initiative had made her more outgoing and social, and she described cycling in general as a way out of her developing depression. Socialising and taking part in CAT's (case 3) actions has greatly improved the quality of her life in that respect.

In the Italian bike-to-school initiative (case 4), the story of Giuliano's son is interesting (IT03). Motivated by his family's example and by participating in projects on sustainable mobility at school, he decided that when he grows up, he does not want to buy a car and always wants to travel by bicycle. Another better story is that of Clara (IT04) who, thanks to the participation in the bike-to-school action with her daughter, regained self-confidence to cycle in traffic and started to use her bike more for short trips around the neighbourhood. In the Italian bike kitchen case (case 5), Tommaso

(IT07) now uses the bicycle as his main means of transport. Tommaso was able to make this change after moving closer to the city centre and meeting in the cycle workshops cycling activists who only travelled by bicycle. This motivated him very much, making him gain competence and feel safe in traffic.

Moreover, there are some better stories on the question of outreach and inclusive recruitment that needs to be further highlighted. Both case 1, De Fietsschool and case 12, the Swedish bike school for immigrant women had developed specific strategies for recruitment based on wider networks and in-depth knowledge about their target groups. Other examples of successfully using established networks are case 6, Ciclopes which successfully engaged vulnerable and marginalised groups thanks to Drive Impact, the initiative's promoter, forming partnerships with local organisations such as the National Association of Street Football in Padre Cruz and Kriativu in Armador. These organisations were instrumental in promoting the initiative and recruiting participants for the various activities conducted as part of the Ciclopes project in both neighbourhoods.

Conclusions

5. Conclusions

RL7 has collected and analysed detailed empirical data on how cycling initiatives and programmes may contribute to behavioural change in vulnerable groups and/or for vulnerable areas, and to cycling inclusion. The task has been formulated around three research questions that are outlined and discussed below.

5.1 Overall conclusions per RL specific research questions

- To what extent and how do cycling initiatives reduce barriers for marginalised groups/individuals to take up cycling?

The studied initiatives all contribute to lowering barriers to cycling for vulnerable and marginalised groups. They do this through very hands-on interventions, by supporting access to bikes and competence in using them, by making cycling available for marginalised and vulnerable groups as an option for everyday transport in often very car-dense contexts. Factors that contribute to behavioural change on an individual level are access to **safe spaces** and **hands-on support** for building cycling competence.

The initiatives also contributed to support **cycling culture** in various ways. By strengthening local and regional cycling **communities** and pro-cycling activism, facilitating social cycling events, and pro-cycling infrastructure such as bike racks and bike-to-school routes. The research findings all point to how important the sense of community was for facilitating change. However, despite efforts to be inclusive, some of the initiatives had problems reaching outside of the typical in-group of convinced cyclists and families (for example, the Italian bike-to-school initiative and bike kitchen).

The time and effort put into supporting the various target groups by the initiatives was highly valued by the participants. The initiatives, by providing platforms for cycling practice, supported building trust for these groups just by 'being there' and making support available. One might say that the initiatives contribute to a **positive** change by making participants understand themselves and their communities as valuable in the Green Deal transition. We note that **the time factor and recourses in terms of volunteers are important** prerequisites to facilitate positive outcomes.

- How do different interventions for cycling inclusion unfold on which groups, and with what gender+ intersectional effects?

The initiatives may lower barriers for participants to learn how to cycle safely, access bikes and support an increase in cycling embrace for the ACCTING target groups, but the transport system does not always allow them to realise change in their everyday lives. **Cycling safety** is a barrier for change and cycling inclusion across all initiatives studied, although with different effects across intersections of gender, age, physical ability, socioeconomic status and geographical location. This is especially so for **seniors and disabled** people taking part in bike schools, and bike-to-school initiatives where **children were dependent upon support by their parents** to cycle in rural and urban contexts. For these groups, cycling is mainly possible within the initiative where they had access to safe spaces for cycling, less so in their everyday lives outside the initiative.

The study made evident several factors that contributed to boosting the capacity for cycling at an individual level. Important outcomes are increased self-sufficiency and capacity building towards

increased cycling and independence. The women who took part in bike schools or cycling promotion initiatives presented the most significant step in terms of change: from no embrace to medium/strong embrace. Partly this can be explained by the women-inclusive learning environments and the participants' motivation to learn how to cycle: For gaining employment, for increased health, wellbeing and independence, and to reduce their transport costs. The interviewed women also talked about cycling with their children as a supporting factor for change. This in turn points to the importance of acknowledging children's role in supporting their parents to take up cycling. Other participants, including senior and disabled persons mentioned social aspects as of particular importance for their participation, since the initiatives helped them break social isolation.

- How can cycling initiatives contribute to an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal?

Any long-lasting achievements are hard to measure within a project like this. However, the outcomes show that the initiatives all contributed in some way to making the Green Deal more just and inclusive. Currently, in many EU-countries and cities, getting more people on bikes and improving the conditions for cycling is the focus of considerable political and public attention. The concept of "smart mobilities" is often used, which places emphasis on technological solutions, which in themselves can be highly exclusive. Thus, the concept fails to connect mobility patterns and needs of low-income groups, it excludes the digitally illiterate, those without debit/credit cards or smartphones, etc. The studied cycling initiatives offer different routes to support by shifting towards more sustainable mobilities. Instead of emphasising technological solutions to the problem of unsustainable transport, the initiatives build social platforms for change and provide the necessary material and social infrastructure for making cycling available for vulnerable and marginalised people. More importantly, they place emphasis on *inclusion* and how to increase diverse users' *capacity* for sustainable mobility.

However, the results also point to the need for more human-centred planning and policy that normalise cycling for groups traditionally facing barriers to take up cycling, i.e. those who depart from the able bodied, young, male norm. The type of initiatives studied in this research line are examples of platforms that can be repeated and multiplied. They are modest, simple and mundane – not necessarily what is normally associated with 'smart', 'high status' and 'high tech' Green Deal projects. **Instead, the studied initiatives emphasise the importance that social infrastructures, cooperation and mutual support can have in realising the European Green Deal.**

5.2 Policy recommendations

The findings show the potential of cycling initiatives to transform mobility practices for vulnerable and marginalised groups and strengthen their capacity to take up more sustainable mobilities. However, concrete opportunities to access and become competent in cycling need to be implemented alongside systemic changes of car-oriented customs to displace habits that reproduce the car norm. The findings indicate the **need for systemic changes of infrastructures and planning to strengthen cycling cultures** to realise the full potential of the studied initiatives.

Some key takeaways for policymakers are outlined below:

- **Providing infrastructure and 'smart solutions' is not enough** for vulnerable groups. Cycling promotion and policy need to create concrete opportunities to access bikes, learn new skills and overcome physical barriers (as also recognised by previous research, van der Kloof, 2022). Policy needs to adopt a holistic view/approach that builds on an understanding that barriers (access, competence and embrace) are interrelated and that all elements need to be reduced to boost inclusive cycling.

- A holistic approach further requires an approach that builds on an intersectional understanding of mobile bodies as simultaneously gendered, raced, aged, (dis)abled, etc. In other words, cycling is not equally accessible for all; it matters if people experience racism and sexism while cycling because this affects their ability to become cyclists. This is also true for disabled people and more senior participants in this study, who found current traffic and cycling lanes too busy and dangerous. A necessary step towards inclusive cycling is to **listen to the initiatives' demands, and to pay attention to context-specific barriers to inclusive and safe cycling.**
- Policymakers also need to **facilitate co-creative projects taking on the forms of the social initiatives covered in this study.** Such cycling promotion could better cover both the social dimensions of cycling in addition to the physical dimensions of safety and accessibility (see Silonsaari, 2025).
- While many initiatives struggle with scarce resources, **securing funds for cycling supporting initiatives** is of great importance. This will secure their contribution to facilitating the impacts we have shown in this study.
- Secured funding can also facilitate their **long-term sustainability**, which is important to build trust in relevant communities of participants. Secure funding is also key for **moving from sporadic interventions with less impact to the forms of well-functioning and structured programmes** for cycling inclusion that some of the initiatives in this study are examples of.

5.3 Research gaps and directions for future research

The social cycling initiatives studied in this research line offer various forms of 'low tech' and bottom-up approaches to support cycling. Future research may address what **long-term impacts** such social cycling initiatives have, especially in disadvantaged neighbourhoods and for marginalised and vulnerable groups. Also, not all cyclists are the same and there is probably no one-size-fits-all solution which can increase cycling opportunities and behaviour among all kinds of groups. More data is needed on who does and who does not have **access to biking** (Vietinghoff 2021), and how it can be improved for different people.

Previous studies have shown that norms around cycling, and the aged and gendered dimensions embedded in these cycling norms, are an important factor influencing cycling uptake among young people over the course of their youth (Schmassman et al., 2024). The Portuguese case studies centring on young people and cycling addressed this, especially the challenge in making cycling 'cool' in the shadow of the car norm. Further studies are needed to evaluate the impact of **transport norms on gender values and change**, and how motivations for change are linked to intersections of gender, age and ethnicity – across **different cultural contexts**.

This study shows the role which **parents** have in supporting or inhibiting change. Time and commitment to supporting (children's) cycling comes through as highly important. Yet, time to support children's cycling was also unevenly distributed. It was foremost middle-class parents with non-immigrant backgrounds who were able to support their children's cycling. Future studies may focus on how to reduce such gaps, paying particular attention to intersections of, among other things, gender, income, work conditions and families' time-spatial obligations.

5.4 Links and crossovers to other policy areas and RLs

There are several overlaps and synergies with the Green Deal policy areas and the seven other ACCTING RLs:

- A synergy with RL8 is the importance of understanding transport habits as conditioned and embedded in everyday life, rather than being merely an individual choice.
- There are also potential synergies with broader themes such as the undervaluing of local (cycling) knowledge (RL1), which has implications for transport planning and for whom the transport system provides for.
- There are potential synergies with RL2 and the importance of nature (being in nature/feeling for nature) as reasons for change.
- There is a crossover with RL3 on the role of communities for sharing knowledge and knowledge transfer (similarities with bike kitchens).
- RL5's focus on self-organisation to get access to food (for instance through urban gardening) and RL6's focus on the role of BUI's for instigating and enabling change both overlaps with RL7's emphasis on cycling initiatives for change. They all highlight the great relevance and potential lying in relatively small-scale, bottom-up initiatives in spreading knowledge, competences, motivation and empowerment to adopt more sustainable behaviours and become part of a social community.

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